

ENTRUST

Project Title	ENsuring Secure and Safe CMD Design with Zero TRUST Principles		
Project Acronym	ENTRUST		
Grant Agreement No	101095634	Type of Action	Research and Innovation Action
Call / Topic	HORIZON-HLTH-2022-IND-13-01		

D3.1 Trust Abstractions and Cryptographic Anchors for CMD Secure Operation

Work Package	WP3 – Trust Modelling, Risk Assessment and Security-by-Design Toolbox		
Lead Beneficiary	TUE		
Contributing Beneficiaries	TUE, SMNS, UPRC, SINTEF, UBITECH		
Due Date	31.03.2024	Actual Date of Submission	10.05.2024
Version	1.0		
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Abstract	<p>In this deliverable we first provide an elaborated action workflow of the operational phases of the ENTRUST framework (Design, Pre-deployment, Runtime). Afterwards, we focus on the specific components of the ENTRUST framework participating in the trust level maintenance process and we provide details on the approach followed in this regard for each component, as well as user stories and functional specifications. The Formal Verification component uses formal methods in order to ensure the correctness of the schemes and security enablers of ENTRUST. The Threat Modelling and Software Verification components are introduced for identifying and formalizing the threat landscape affecting the device, as well as their interconnectivity with the Risk Assessment component. Furthermore, the Protection Profiles are defined containing the trustworthiness attributes and security enablers associated with these, and by the end we outline the Digital Twins used in order to simulate attacks and potentially malicious behaviour in order to identify new threats or vulnerabilities.</p>		

Keywords

Connected Medical Devices, Formal Verification, Software Verification, Threat Modelling, Risk Assessment, Trust Assessment, Digital Twins

Versioning and contribution history

Version	Date	Author	Notes
0.01	15.12.2023	Ivan Kurtev (TUE)	Initial ToC
0.02	29.01.2024	Robert Şolcă (SMNS)	Provide chapter "Threat Modelling and Software Verification"
0.03	29.01.2024	Cristina Vlădărean (SMNS)	Initial "Conclusions"
0.04	02.02.2024	Ivan Kurtev, Leonard Tudorache (TUE)	Provide chapter "Introduction": purpose and structure. Chapter "Formal Verification of SDLM"
0.05	05.02.2024	Vaios Bolgouras (UPRC)	Provide chapter "Trust abstractions and protection files"
0.06	20.02.2024	Dimitris Karras (UBITECH)	Provide chapter "Trust and Risk Assessment Framework"
0.07	27.02.2024	Cristina Vlădărean (SMNS)	Edit "Glossary": abbreviations. Edit "Conclusions": status summarization.
0.08	01.03.2024	Robert Şolcă (SMNS)	Update chapter "Threat Modelling and Software Verification": include integration with Risk Assessment, Software Verification architecture, Deployment
0.09	06.03.2024	Cristina Vlădărean (SMNS)	Prepare for review (figures list, tables list, cross references)
0.10	07.03.2024	Robert Şolcă (SMNS)	Added threat modelling and software verification user stories
0.11	25.03.2024	Robert Şolcă (SMNS)	Updated bibliography
0.12	25.03.2024	Arda Goknil (SINTEF)	Provide chapter "Digital Twin"
0.13	04.04.2024	Dimitris Karras (UBITECH)	Provide chapter "Maintenance of Trust Level of CMDs in ENTRUST"
0.14	10.04.2024	Robert Şolcă (SMNS), Dimitris Karras (UBITECH), Georgios Petychakis (UPRC), Arda Goknil (SINTEF), Leonard Tudorache (TUE)	Provide engineering stories
0.15	26.04.2024	Robert Şolcă (SMNS), Dimitris Karras (UBITECH), Vaios Bolgouras, Georgios Petychakis (UPRC), Arda Goknil (SINTEF), Ivan Kurtev (TUE)	Address review suggestions
0.16	29.04.2024	Cristina Vlădărean (SMNS)	Submission-ready version: acronyms, cross references, formatting
0.17	30.04.2024	Cristina Vlădărean (SMNS)	Final version
1.0	10.05.2024	Stavroula-Isidora Giannakandropoulou (UNIS)	Final review and submission

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Project co-funded by the European Commission in the Horizon Programme		
Nature of the deliverable:	R	
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open	X
SEN	Sensitive, confidential to ENTRUST project and Commission Services	

- * R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
- DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
- DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.
- OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.
- DMP: Data Management Plan

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Term	Description
AAA	Authentication, Authorization and Accounting framework
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AK	Authentication Key
API	Application Programming Interface
ATL	Actual Trustworthiness Level
CAPEC	Common Attack Pattern Enumeration and Classification
CIV	Configuration Integrity Verification
CMD	Connected Medical Device
CPE	Common Platform Enumeration
CSP	Cloud Service Provider
CVE	Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures
CVSS	Common Vulnerability Scoring System
CWE	Common Weakness Enumeration
D2.1	ENTRUST deliverable D2.1 “ENTRUST Reference Architecture – Initial Release”
D3.1	ENTRUST deliverable D3.1 “Trust Abstractions & Cryptographic Anchors for CMD Secure Operation”
DB	Database
DDoS	Distributed Denial of Service
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
DHCP	Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol
DM	Domain Manager
DT	Digital Twin
EAP	Extensible Authentication Protocol
eBPF	extended Berkeley Packet Filter
eMUD	Extended MUD
HDO	Healthcare Delivery Organization
IOC	Indices of Compromise
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Internet Protocol
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KDK	Key-derivation Key
LLM	Large Language Model
MAC	Message Authentication Code
MCM	Modified Counter Mode

Term	Description
MISP	Open-Source Threat Intelligence and Sharing Platform (https://www.misp-project.org)
MITM	Man-in-the-Middle attack
MITRE	MITRE is not an acronym but is a thought-about company name to represent the substantial cybersecurity knowledge base funded by NIST (https://mitre.org)
MITRE ATT&CK	MITRE ATT&CK is a globally accessible knowledge base of adversary tactics and techniques based on real-world observations (https://attack.mitre.org). ATT&CK stands for Adversary Tactics, Techniques and Common Knowledge.
ML	Machine Learning
MSK	Master Session Key
MUD	Manufacturer Usage Description (https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc8520)
NGINX	NGINX is a free, open-source, high-performance HTTP server and reverse proxy, as well as an IMAP/POP3 proxy server (https://www.nginx.com)
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology (at the U.S. Department of Commerce)
NVD	NIST National Vulnerability Database
NLP	Natural Language Processing
PSK	Pre-Shared Key
RA	Risk Assessment
RTL	Required Trustworthiness Level
SA	Swarm Attestation
SDLM	Secure Device Lifecycle Management
TAF	Trust Assessment Framework
TAM	Trust Assessment Manager
TDE	Trust Decision Engine
TEK	Transient EAP Key
TI	Threat Intelligence
TLEE	Trustworthiness Level Expression Engine
TM	Trust Model
TPM	Trusted Platform Module
TSM	Trust Source Manager
TSQ	Trust Source Quantifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WBAN	Wireless Body Area Networks
WP3	ENTRUST work package 3 "Trust Modelling, Risk Assessment and Security-by-design toolbox"
YARA	YARA is the name of a tool primarily used in malware research and detection (https://yara.readthedocs.io/)

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Executive Summary

One of the core tenets of ENTRUST entails the provision of operational assurance to **Connected Medical Devices** in order to ensure that they are in a trustworthy state throughout their operational lifecycle. This process begins from the manufacturing, i.e., **Design phase** of the device, where the Manufacturer conceptualizes the functionalities of the device and envisions its implementation in accordance with the requirements set forth in the latest standards and regulations. During this phase, the device is evaluated in isolation, without considering the requirements, architecture, and infrastructure of the medical organization where it will eventually be deployed. Afterwards, the **Pre-deployment** phase entails the connection of the device to the infrastructure of the medical organization where the device is intended to be deployed, where the System Administrator is able to provide additional information on the CMDs belonging to the system architecture, as well as domain-specific requirements. Finally, the **Runtime** phase is concerned with the provision of operational assurance of the device using the security enablers of ENTRUST (e.g., remote attestation schemes), as well as the deployment of appropriate mitigation measures in case a threat or vulnerability is identified. In this deliverable, we provide a detailed overview of the components participating in the maintenance of the trust levels of CMDs in ENTRUST, including engineering stories and functional specifications for each component.

The first component to be analysed in this deliverable is the **Formal Verification** module in Chapter 3, which aims to enable the analysis of requirements that can be verified using formal mathematical methods. This component is in line with the security-by-design system development approach followed by ENTRUST towards increasing confidence in the trustworthiness of the system, and the purpose of this component is the *identification of security flaws in early stages of development, since mitigating such flaws after the deployment of the system may lead to disproportionately high maintenance costs*. The process followed by the Formal Verification module entails the formal verification of security enablers and protocols provided by the ENTRUST framework, such as the **secure enrolment** scheme, the **remote attestation** schemes, and the **cryptographic schemes** of ENTRUST. The requirements that can be verified may include **integrity, confidentiality, authenticity**, etc. Note that requirements that cannot be verified during the Design phase need to be attested during the Runtime phase.

Next, in Chapter 4, we focus on the **Threat Modelling** component, which is responsible for identifying the types of threats and vulnerabilities typically affecting the type of CMD developed by the Manufacturer. The purpose of this component is to *formulate a threat landscape for the CMD including the latest identified vulnerabilities, in order to enable the Security Administrator to formulate a mitigation strategy based on the available security enablers*. Note that the Threat Modelling component needs to be able to provide threat intelligence information in a manner that facilitates integration with other tools. For example, in order to assess the risk associated with each threat and vulnerability, this data needs to be provided to the **Risk Assessment** component in an appropriate (JSON) format in a manner that includes all relevant information (e.g., likelihood, impact, and frequency of each threat). In addition, the **Software Verification** component aims to *investigate the software installed on the CMD in order to identify any structural or development issues that may lead to the introduction of vulnerabilities or other security issues*. This is achieved by scanning binaries for malicious patterns that may be indicated by the aforementioned threat landscape, and may affect not only the CMD itself, but also the medical system where it will be deployed as a whole.

Chapter 5 is dedicated to the process followed towards the definition of the **Trust Abstractions** leading to the formulation of the **Protection Profiles** of the device. Note that *the Protection Profile of a device contains not only the static security properties of the CMD, but also the dynamic security elements of ENTRUST that are able to address the identified threat landscape*. To this end, ENTRUST builds upon the state-of-the-art advancements in the definition of **Manufacturer**

Usage Descriptions (MUD) and **extended MUD (eMUD)** in order to construct Protection Profiles tailored to the needs and requirements of medical devices and Healthcare Delivery Organizations. Information included in these Profiles may include information such as device identification, configuration details, types of threats and vulnerabilities affecting the device, as well as attestation enablers and mitigation strategies appropriate for each identified threat and vulnerability.

Finally, in Chapter 6, we focus on the **Digital Twins**, which entail the creation of dynamic virtual replicas of physical systems, namely the CMDs participating in the types of healthcare organizations targeted by ENTRUST. *The purpose of Digital Twins is the real-time monitoring, analysis, and simulation of threats in a safe and controlled environment, so that the actual device is not harmed.* Thus, the Digital Twins in the context of ENTRUST leverage the trace information collected by the Device Tracer in the context of an attestation operation in order to pinpoint the cause behind the failed attestation. Thus, we are able to understand the potential impact of the identified threats and vulnerabilities, evaluate the effectiveness of existing security measures, and assist in deciding on whether additional measures are needed in order to mitigate the identified vulnerabilities. The outcomes of the Digital Twins are forwarded to the Risk Assessment component, in order to perform a re-evaluation of the risk affecting the CMD, as well as the system as a whole.

Considering all the above, this deliverable is focused on the action workflow of ENTRUST with regard to the maintenance of the trust level of CMDs throughout their operational lifecycle. Note that this process entails the calculation of the **Required Trust Level** of the device against which its trustworthiness is evaluated, as well as the **Actual Trust Level** of the device based on the trustworthiness evidence collected by the device as part of attestation processes. Note that the ATL is calculated by the **Trust Assessment Framework**, which is defined in this deliverable through engineering stories and functional specifications, and it will be described in further detail in subsequent deliverables. Throughout the remainder of this deliverable, we elaborate on how all the aforementioned components participate in the trust level maintenance process, their positioning within the ENTRUST framework, and the functional specifications of each component.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

One of the core tenets of ENTRUST is the maintenance of the trust level of Connected Medical Devices (CMDs) throughout their operational lifecycle, towards achieving the provision of secure and reliable healthcare services by the Healthcare Delivery Organizations (HDOs) they operate within. As outlined in D2.1 [1], in the context of ENTRUST, the device lifecycle considered by ENTRUST is split into three core phases. The **Design phase** includes all actions taken at the side of the Manufacturer, before the device is actually deployed to the target medical domain. The **Pre-deployment phase** entails all actions taken after the manufacturing process is completed and before it is integrated into the infrastructure of the target organization, including the secure enrolment process, which generates all required cryptographic material for participating in the ENTRUST framework. The **Runtime phase** refers to all actions taken in order to provide operational assurance to the CMD during its normal operation, such as attestation processes.

In general, trustworthiness and trust relationships are central to the security of medical and healthcare organizations. Such systems may be complex and large-scale, and they rely on the correct provisioning of services or input data from a CMD to another. Thus, **trust relationships** are formed between the CMDs, where a trustor needs to rely on a trustee in order to provide its own service. Following the **zero-trust paradigm**, this trust should not be blindly assumed and no CMD can be considered trusted by default, but trust must be established through the provision of the appropriate trustworthiness evidence and analysis. In ENTRUST, as outlined in D2.1 [1], each CMD is characterized by a set of **attributes or characteristics** based on which its trustworthiness can be evaluated. Each one of these can be evaluated based on the appropriate types of **trustworthiness evidence**, which is collected by the monitoring and tracing mechanisms of the CMD, and the trustworthiness of a device is based on the attestation of a set of attributes, which are specified in the **Protection Profile** of the device.

For ensuring that the trust level of the CMD is at an acceptable level throughout all the aforementioned phases, ENTRUST follows an approach centred around the calculation of the **Required Trustworthiness Level (RTL)** of the device based on the information that is already known and available about the type of the device, such as the threats and vulnerabilities typically affecting the device, as well as the likelihood and the impact associated with each of them. Afterwards, based on the collection of the aforementioned evidence on the selected set of attributes the **Actual Trustworthiness Level (ATL)** is calculated by the **Trust Assessment Framework (TAF)**, and is afterwards compared with the RTL in order to verify whether additional mitigation measures need to be taken in order to ensure the trustworthiness of the CMD. These may include the deployment of secure software/firmware updates, or the definition of new attestation actions based on the identified vulnerabilities.

In this deliverable, in Chapter 2, we first provide an elaborated action workflow of the process outlined above, split into the three aforementioned operational phases of the ENTRUST framework (Design, Pre-deployment, Runtime). Afterwards, and throughout the remainder of this deliverable, we focus on the specific components of the ENTRUST framework participating in the trust level maintenance process and we provide details on the approach followed in this regard for each component, as well as user stories and functional specifications. Specifically, Chapter 3 is focused on the **Formal Verification** component, which uses formal methods in order to ensure the correctness of the schemes and security enablers of ENTRUST. Chapter 4 details the **Threat Modelling** and **Software Verification** components for identifying and formalizing the threat landscape affecting the device, as well as their interconnectivity with the **Risk Assessment (RA)** component. Chapter 5 focuses on the definition of the **Protection Profiles** containing the trustworthiness attributes and security enablers associated with these, and Chapter 6 outlines the

Digital Twins used in order to simulate attacks and potentially malicious behaviour in order to identify new threats or vulnerabilities.

Within the scope of the ENTRUST project, deliverable D3.1 is the first planned deliverable in Work Package 3 (WP3). It focuses on trust abstractions and cryptographic anchors that support the secure operation of CMDs. More concretely, it reports the current progress of **Tasks 3.1-3.3**. In the context of the ENTRUST reference architecture, WP3 is concerned mainly with components used in the design phase. It also serves as enabler for functionalities performed at runtime phase. The objectives of WP3 are:

- I. The definition of formally verified trust models, crypto mechanisms, and security protocols to be used throughout the CMD lifecycle.
- II. The development of advanced verification methods for software validation.
- III. The development of a continuous risk assessment methodology along with a method for risk identification in CMDs.
- IV. The identification of the gaps that need to be protected by the runtime defensive technologies of ENTRUST, as the system properties (for runtime attestation) in the update MUD Protection Profiles.

WP3 contains 5 tasks, the first three are in the scope of this deliverable:

- Task 3.1: Formal Verification of Secure Device Lifecycle Management, addressing objective (i)
- Task 3.2: Threat Modelling and Software Verification, addressing objectives (ii) and (iii)
- Task 3.3: Trust Abstractions and Protection Profiles, addressing objective (iv)

For each task the deliverable reports on: (a) the overall vision and approach taken in the task; (b) current progress; (c) expected next steps.

1.2 Structure of the Document

The remainder of this deliverable is structured as follows:

Chapter 2 provides the action workflow of the entire ENTRUST framework, with particular focus on the process followed for the maintenance of trust levels of CMDs in ENTRUST, as well as the positioning of the various WP3 artefacts within this process, which will be analysed in further detail in the following Chapters.

Chapter 3 reports results from Task 3.1. It gives an overview of tool-assisted formal verification of security properties in communication protocols and makes a choice of several tools that will be used to verify the models developed in this task (namely VerifPal). It then proceeds with the refinement of the onboarding phase of the CMD defining the used crypto primitives and sequences of actions and identifying its security requirements. The refined model is encoded in the language of VerifPal. The chapter reports and reflects on the verification results and concludes with the expected next steps.

Chapter 4 reports results from Task 3.2 and contains two main parts: Threat Modelling architecture and flow, and Software Verification architecture and flow. Both outline the overall vision how these two objectives will be addressed in the project. In addition, Chapter 4 outlines the principles behind the interfacing of the Threat Modelling component with the Risk Assessment component for exchanging threat intelligence information.

Chapter 5 reports results from Task 3.3 and outlines an approach for extending the Protection Profile structure with custom fields. Thus, this Chapter outlines the process for the definition of

Protection Profiles tailored to the medical domain, so that they include both the types of attributes associated with CMDs, and the appropriate attestation tasks.

Chapter 6 is focused on the Digital Twins and their use for simulating attacks and potentially malicious behaviour based on the collected evidence, so that new threats and vulnerabilities can be identified and subsequently appropriate mitigation actions can be implemented.

Chapter 7 concludes the deliverable summarizing the main results and outlining the most important next steps.

2 Maintenance of Trust Level of CMDs in ENTRUST

One core tenet of ENTRUST is the provision of the ability to **monitor and maintain the trust level and the trustworthiness of the state of all medical devices**, referred to as Connected Medical Devices, comprising a service graph chain as part of the infrastructure of a medical organization domain. At a high level, the overarching goal of this approach is to compare the **Required Trust Level** with the **Actual Trust Level** of the device, in order to be able to determine if the device is in a trustworthy state, or if further actions are needed in order to address identified threats or vulnerabilities and bring the ATL of the device to an acceptable level.

In this regard, ENTRUST offers a wide variety of components and methodologies as part of an overall **Trust Assessment Framework** that enables the evaluation of the trustworthiness of the CMDs in all operational phases, starting from the Manufacturing Phase and including the Pre-deployment and Runtime Phases, and the actions performed in this regard can be split into two core categories: (i) actions for the calculation of the RTL, and (ii) actions for the calculation of the ATL. In this deliverable, we focus on the former category, which includes the correctness of the employed protocols with the **Formal Verification** component, the identification of existing threats and vulnerabilities using the **Threat Modelling and Software Verification** component, the identification of new vulnerabilities using **Digital Twins**, the inclusion of trust parameters to be attested in the **Protection Profile** of the device, and the identification of trust levels against risk scores with the **Risk Assessment** component. Note that the actions pertaining to the latter category include the **runtime attestation** schemes that are able to attest the correctness of the required trust properties during runtime fall within the scope of WP4, and are analysed in further detail in D4.1 [2].

2.1 ENTRUST action workflow

In D2.1, we provided a high-level overview of the reference architecture of ENTRUST, including the action workflow throughout the operational lifecycle of the device. Here, we elaborate on this workflow, by positioning the aforementioned components and methodologies within the overall reference architecture.

Figure 2.1.1: ENTRUST action workflow - Design phase.

Design phase: The steps of this phase are depicted at a high level in **Error! Reference source not found.** and are elaborated in the following.

1. During the design phase of a CMD, the device Manufacturer begins with the initial conceptualization of the device, focusing on the medical scope of the domain where the device is intended to be used. This includes the definition of specifications, such as essential security and compliance requirements in accordance with the latest healthcare standards, legislation, and medical safety protocols. Recall that, in D2.1 [1], we provided detailed information on the approach to be followed with regard to the harmonization of the medical standards and their consideration in the context of ENTRUST.
2. Given the initial design of the CMD, including the device capabilities, the **Threat Modelling** component (Section 4.3) is responsible for an **initial identification of potential threats and vulnerabilities** pertaining to the context of the device. The initial phase of this process includes **gathering data regarding the threat landscape using a web scraper**. Note that this component is also connected to the **NIST National Vulnerability Database (NVD)** and the **MITRE Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE)**, which are known databases containing vulnerabilities and attack methods. Then, a **Large Language Model (LLM)** is used in order to create context or to fine-tune it.
3. The **Software Verification** module (Section 4.6) receives information on the identified threat landscape in order to create a testing plan based on various intelligence sources, using **Indices of Compromise (IOC)**. This component consists of a binary code analyser and a source code analyser which are used in order to identify whether the files or binaries related to the target device demonstrate vulnerabilities or malicious patterns, based on the previously outlined process.
4. Upon completion of this processing, the structured threat intelligence information is forwarded to a database, which acts as a repository to store and organize this intelligence, so that it can be made accessible for further analysis.
5. Using the collected intelligence, as well as specific information regarding the specific device and threats that have been previously identified, the Threat Modelling component creates a threat model, which is sent to the **Risk Assessment** component in a JSON format in order to perform an initial risk calculation prior to the deployment of the device to the target medical domain.
6. After the risk quantification of each identified threat and vulnerability is complete, the **Attack Validation** component becomes active. This utilizes a **Digital Twin (DT)** in order to perform attack testing, validation, and resilience checks against the identified threat models and attack vectors. Note that the DT is a virtual, container-based environment that acts as the digital representation of the device, and is used in order to replicate identified threats and evaluate mitigation actions (through security and attestation policies) in a controlled setting. This approach allows for enhanced forecasting, detection, and prevention of vulnerabilities so that the appropriate mitigation measures can be implemented in real-world scenarios. Note that we are also currently investigating the possibility for the Digital Twins to provide information regarding the **likelihood of the identified threats**, as well as the **severity of the potential attacks**, which can be used in order to facilitate the calculation of an accurate risk score by the Risk Assessment component. Further information on the DT is provided in Chapter 6.
7. The next step in the Design phase is the formal verification of the trust models that cover the entire lifecycle of the CMD, including both behavioural and cryptographic aspects of the CMD functions (e.g., types of keys and encryption). This will ensure their correctness regarding the previously defined requirements pertaining to security, privacy, and trust. This is performed by the **Formal Verification** component and is able to verify the schemes implemented as part of the ENTRUST framework, such as the **secure enrolment and**

- bootstrapping, the remote attestation schemes, and the lightweight crypto schemes.** The Formal Verification component is further analysed in Chapter 3.
8. The **Risk Assessment** module receives the aforementioned information from the Threat Modelling component and the Digital Twin in order to perform an **initial calculation of the Required Trust Level** of the device. Note that this is performed based on the characteristics of the device in isolation, prior to its deployment to the target medical organization. In addition, as this is performed during the design-time phase, this does not take into consideration the topology of the domain where the device will be deployed. The RA module will be analysed in further detail in D3.2 [3], but the definitions of the relevant functional specifications are provided in Section 4.9 of the present deliverable.
 9. The final step in the Design phase is the **creation of the Protection Profiles by the manufacturer**, which include detailed security specifications designed to address the identified risks associated with specific functionalities of the CMD. Specifically, Protection Profiles in the context of ENTRUST extend the **MUD** profiles, as standardised by the IETF in RFC 8520. Thus, we construct a definition of **extended MUD profiles** in order to establish a continuous trust verification process, aiming to adapt to the shifting landscape of threats and operational challenges. These eMUDs cater to the dynamic and complex nature of modern healthcare environments, by providing the capability to apply a weakness and vulnerability management approach, which serves as a comprehensive method for understanding and mitigating risks. Further information on these Protection Profiles is provided in Chapter 5.

Figure 2.1.2: ENTRUST action workflow - Pre-deployment phase.

Pre-Deployment Phase: The steps of this phase are depicted at a high level in **Error! Reference source not found.** and are elaborated in the following.

10. Once the design phase is completed, the device is deployed to the medical organization where it is intended to be installed. Note that, up until this phase, all processes performed considered the device in isolation, i.e., not as part of the overall network infrastructure of the target medical domain. Thus, the **security administrator** of the domain needs to provide information to the **Risk Assessment** component regarding the network topology, as well as security, safety, and privacy requirements specific to the target organization. Note that in the context of ENTRUST, we do not consider identity privacy (i.e., privacy of the identity of the user or medical device), but mainly **attribute privacy**. The purpose of this consideration is to prevent malicious third parties from obtaining information that may contain details about the inner workings of the device, thus preventing **implementation disclosure attacks**. Note that, based on the newly available information, it is possible for the Risk Assessment to **calculate an updated RTL of the device**, which subsequently will be evaluated against the ATL in the context of the target domain.
11. Recall that, during the Design phase, the **Formal Verification** component performed a model-based verification process on the security enablers available to perform various security operations on the device. However, it is possible that at that time, the verification process does not converge, potentially due to the complexity of the schemes and the properties to be verified. Furthermore, during the pre-deployment phase, it is possible that the Security Administrator provides additional security requirements, which can be included in the Formal Verification process. Therefore, in such a case, this process is executed again during the pre-deployment phase considering the additional provided requirements and the convergence of the process is re-evaluated. Further details on this process are given in Chapter 2.
12. After this information has been provided by the security administrator, the Risk Assessment module performs a re-quantification of risk considering the network topology and the specifics of the targeted environment, and generates an **attack path calculation** based on the interdependencies between existing assets in the network and the asset cartography. Thus, it calculates the **updated risk score**, the **impact per vulnerability**, and the calculated **attack paths**, and forwards this information to the Domain Manager.
13. Following this analysis, the updated information about the network topology and the identified attack paths is forwarded to the **Digital Twin**, so that it is able to consider the capability for validating various types of attacks and facilitating the assessment of their impact on the network infrastructure.
14. The Domain Manager retrieves the **Protection Profile** of the device and extracts the policies containing the security recommendations and mitigation actions contained therein. Note that these are selected based on the security enablers provided by the ENTRUST framework, such as Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV) or other remote attestation enablers, and are further described in D4.1 [2] and subsequent WP4 deliverables.
15. The Protection Profiles are customized by the security administrator and forwarded to the Trust Controls component, which calculates the updated RTL based on the information regarding the network topology of the organization. The updated Protection Profiles are deployed to the Domain Manager.
16. Afterwards, in order to be registered as part of the network infrastructure of the medical organization, the **secure enrolment** process is applied, which entails the generation of the required cryptographic material and keys required so that the device is able to utilize the security enablers of ENTRUST. This process includes two phases: (i) the **Manufacturer Bootstrapping** phase, which refers to the actions required for assigning and certifying the unique ID of the device from the perspective of the Manufacturer, and (ii) the **Domain Bootstrapping** phase, which contains the actions required for the registration of the device into the infrastructure of the target organization. Note that a high-level description of the

secure enrolment process has been provided in D2.1 [1], and a detailed description of the scheme will be provided in D4.1 [2].

Figure 2.1.3: ENTRUST action workflow - Runtime phase.

Runtime Phase: The steps of this phase are depicted at a high level in Figure 2.1.3 and are elaborated in the following.

- During the runtime operation of the CMD, it may be required to verify the correctness of the device, acting as the **Prover**, to a different device acting as a **Verifier**. Note that the entity acting as the Verifier depends on the use case, and may be for instance the **Domain Manager**, a **gateway device**, a **different CMD**, or an external **certification/auditing body** aiming to verify the correctness of the device. The attestation schemes provided as part of the ENTRUST framework are further outlined as part of WP4, and specifically in D4.1 [2] and D4.2 [4]. For instance, the provided schemes include **Configuration Integrity Verification** for verifying the correctness of the configuration state of the device, and **Swarm Attestation (SA)** for verifying the correctness of multiple devices simultaneously, in a manner that is more computationally efficient than attesting each device individually. In order to perform a runtime trust assessment process, there are two possible scenarios: (i) CMDs which have the capability to perform asymmetric crypto (i.e., have the capability to manage credentials and certificates), such as gateway devices, retrieve the **eMUD Protection Profile of the CMD from the ledger** and extract the types of evidence needed, as well as the attestation enabler to be executed, and (ii) devices that are only able to create symmetric keys through their PUF, communicate with the **Domain Manager** and **directly collect the required types of evidence**.

18. In the former case, the MUD URL is sent from the CMD to the Domain Manager. If the corresponding Protection Profile is available on the ledger, the Domain Manager retrieves the Profile, including the attestation challenge and the corresponding sources of trust required to attest to the correctness of specific properties. In the latter case, this communication is not needed.
19. If the Verifier device is different than the Domain Manager, the aforementioned information is forwarded to the Verifier so that the attestation process is initiated. A high-level overview of the action workflow of the attestation process is outlined in D2.1 [1], and the cryptographic details of those schemes fall within the scope of WP4. Specifically, initial descriptions are provided in D4.1 [2] and will be further developed and elaborated in D4.2 [4].
20. As a result of the applied attestation process, the **Trust Assessment** component is responsible for the calculation of the ATL of the device based on the attested properties. Some information on this process is provided in Section 4.9, and the Trust Assessment scheme will be described in detail in D3.2 [3]. Note that a high-level description of the Trust Assessment process was provided in D2.1 [1], and involves various sub-components such as the **Trust Model Manager (TMM)** for expressing and specifying the required information to perform Trust Assessment based on Trust Model templates, the **Trust Source Manager (TSM)** for enabling the management of all trust sources pertaining to the attributes specified in the Protection Profile of the device, the **Trustworthiness Level Expression Engine (TLEE)** for calculating and expressing the trustworthiness level of the device, the **Trust Decision Engine (TDE)** for making a decision on if the ATL is adequate compared to the RTL, and the **Trust Assessment Manager (TAM)** which acts as an orchestrator between all aforementioned components.
21. If $ATL < RTL$, this constitutes an **indication of risk**, and indicates that actions need to be taken in order to identify the cause behind the failed attestation, as well as to implement mitigation measures for any identified threats and/or software/firmware patches to the CMD. To this end, the traces collected by the monitoring/tracing mechanisms of the device are forwarded to the **Digital Twin (TD)** so that the process that led to the failed attestation can be emulated. An initial description of this process is provided in Chapter 6, and further details will be provided in subsequent deliverables. Various aspects of this process are currently being investigated, such as the possibility to predict the **likelihood of the occurrence of identified vulnerabilities**. This information can then be forwarded to the **Risk Assessment** component, so that the risk graph can be updated based on the newly available information.
22. Recall that the **Formal Verification** component previously followed a model-based approach in order to formally verify the fulfilment of the security requirements defined by the Manufacturer during the design phase, as well as the Security Administrator during the pre-deployment phase. However, it is also possible to **use information collected by the Tracer in order to formally verify the fulfilment of these security requirements during runtime**. This process is further elaborated in Chapter 3.
23. Based on all processing performed following a failed attestation, it is possible that a patch or software/firmware update needs to be deployed to the device in order to address any newly identified threats or vulnerabilities. This information is forwarded to both the **Digital Twin** and the **Formal Verification** so that they can be considered in subsequent re-evaluations of the device. Afterwards, the **Protection Profile of the CMD is updated** in order to include any new attestation schemes that can be used in order to mitigate the newly identified threats and vulnerabilities, as well as the **trust attributes to be attested** in the context of these attestation schemes.

Throughout the remainder of this deliverable, we provide further information on the operation of all the components outlined in the above action workflow in the context of the ENTRUST framework, their interactions with other components, as well as the approach followed for their

design and implementation, also considering the advancements in the state-of-the-art and the innovations of ENTRUST in each respective scientific domain. We also provide a set of **user and engineering stories** describing the operation of each of these components at a high level, and we afterwards provide **functional specifications** that give a more granular representation of the capabilities of each component and their use as part of the ENTRUST framework.

3 Formal Verification of Secure Device Lifecycle Management: an Illustration of the Modelling and Verification of ENTRUST Onboarding and Bootstrapping

The role of the Formal Verification component within the ENTRUST architecture is to check if the design of the CMD satisfies the security requirements already identified in deliverable D2.1. It operates mainly at design time and contributes to the calculation of the device RTL. This component specifies and uses models of the critical security protocols and schemes of ENTRUST and checks if the security properties (formulated explicitly in a suitable formal language) hold for the given models. To accomplish this, the Formal Verification component will utilize state-of-the-art security protocol verification tools such as ProVerif and Tamarin, as well as other formal verification tools where needed. To this end, the component is crucial in realizing one of the essential rationales of the ENTRUST approach: to monitor and attest at runtime only those properties that cannot be formally verified at design time.

In general, the process of formal verification admits situations where no conclusive result can be produced due to, for example, a combination of complex models and/or security requirements. In these cases, the component may resort to performing verification of requirements on information collected at runtime by the ENTRUST Tracer, an approach known as runtime verification. The specifics of this situation are elaborated further in this chapter.

The past decade witnessed a proliferation of tools for formal verification of security protocols resulting in 2-3 mature tools that stand out in the survey and comparison papers available in the literature. Although these tools are the natural choice for performing the verification tasks, we observe that they employ challenging specification languages and pose a significant learning curve to the practitioners. A detailed overview and state-of-the-art analysis of these tools are given in section 3.5 in this chapter.

3.1 Objectives and Context

This chapter reports on the overall vision and current progress of Task 3.1, part of ENTRUST WP3.

Task 3.1 aims to define formally verified trust models that cover the entire lifecycle of the CMD. The models include both behavioural (e.g. protocols) and cryptographic aspects of the CMD functions (e.g. type of keys and encryption). The formal verification of these models will ensure their correctness regarding the requirements for security, privacy, and trust. The models capture the essential aspects of the device lifecycle. The most important schemes include secure bootstrapping and onboarding, secure communication, remote attestation, software updates, among others. The verification can be done in two ways: via manual mathematical proofs and via (semi-) automated verification using dedicated tools. The choice will be made based on the nature of the properties to be verified, still giving priority to an automated approach whenever possible.

An additional objective of Task 3.1 is to provide models that can be easy to implement over a multitude of devices on a platform as generic as possible. The goal is to design, by relying on secure modes of operation, schemes that can be implemented on any CMD, by system designers who are not aware of the physical threat landscape of the deployment. The task also aims at proposing a test implementation to validate the concept.

It should be noted that the formal verification component itself is used at design time and operates on the backend. In case the runtime verification is needed it can be deployed on device and even on the digital twin component.

This deliverable illustrates our vision by modelling and verification of the ENTRUST onboarding phase as initially defined in the ENTRUST reference architecture available in deliverable D2.1. As a first step (section 3.2), the generic and high-level model from D2.1 is refined until a sufficient level of detail is reached that allows formal specification. The resulting refined model provides description of the interactions among the relevant parties in terms of messages, their parameters and performed actions. It also contains information about the hierarchy of the used keys and how they are obtained. Requirements for the onboarding phase are identified and related to the ENTRUST generic requirements (section 3.4). The expected adversarial model is discussed in section 3.4. Having a model and requirements at hand, they are encoded in the specification language of an automated protocol verification tool. Before this step, an overview of tool-assisted security protocol verification is given in the section 3.6. Section 3.7 shows the model of the onboarding phase specified in the VerifPal tool. Section 3.8 discusses the verification results. Section 3.8 presents detailed user stories that refine the engineering stories as described in the beginning of this chapter. Finally, section 3.10 concludes the chapter about Task 3.1.

3.2 Engineering Stories

We give a number of engineering stories that outline the intention and the operation of this component in the context of the overall ENTRUST architecture.

STORY-I: As a verification engineer, I want to create a verification artefact repository that collects the results of the various verification activities and maps them to the system architecture.

Objective:

The objective is to create a repository that collects information about the performed verification activities, how they are related to the system requirements and to the part of the system architecture that implements these requirements. A typical verification activity involves a property to be verified, a model that has to exhibit this property and a result of the verification. The property and the model are usually expressed in a specialized notation. The repository collects this information and connects it to the high-level system specification thus allowing traceability to high level requirements and system components.

Motivation:

The motivation is to enable analysis of which requirements can be formally verified and which cannot. Requirements that cannot be verified during the design phase need to be attested during the runtime phase. The main difference between the design time and runtime phase is that during the design time verification all possible executions of the model are explored and verified, while during runtime the property is verified against one concrete execution based on observations collected by the tracer. At design time the exploration of all possible executions is computationally expensive and may lead to state space explosion where the verifier does not converge, a phenomenon well known in formal verification. In this case, runtime verification is a suitable technique that is less computationally expensive since only the observed execution paths are verified.

The verification of security requirements involves identification of the key protocols to be verified and their requirements such as integrity, confidentiality, authenticity etc. The repository enables mapping the output of the verification activities to the system requirements.

Building Blocks:

The main building block is the repository itself which is in essence a traceability matrix that relates: system requirements, their refined specifications (amenable to formal verification), the used formal model, the corresponding part of the system architecture from which the formal model is

derived, and the result of the verification. Depending on the complexity of the model and the requirement, the result can be success, failure, and unknown (for example, the verification process does not terminate within a reasonable time frame). In the last case, the verification can be performed at runtime or using thorough testing, for example, by using model-based testing or concolic testing.

STORY-II: As a verification engineer, I want to check the correctness of parts of the operation and communication protocols of the target system, with regard to a set of properties.

Objective:

The objective is to formally verify the correctness of the used protocols by using specialized verification tools (state of the art analysis for such tools is provided in this chapter).

Motivation:

The ability to apply security-by-design approach in system development increases the confidence in the trustworthiness of the system and helps identifying security flaws in the early development stages. System design that is not formally verified increases the risk of design and implementation errors that are exhibited during system operation when fixing them may be too costly.

Building Blocks:

We plan to reuse existing state-of-the-art verification tools specifically tailored towards protocol and security verification and to augment them with a novel front-end that raises the level of abstraction in the specification of the models and the properties to be verified.

STORY-III: As a verification engineer, I want to check the compliance of all design, security, and trust assessment protocols with regards to the requirements as defined by the medical standards.

Objective:

The main objective is to support formal verification of the system design against known requirements mandated by the medical and other relevant standards already identified in D2.1 as well as any specific requirements that the system administrator may pose after the device has been deployed.

Motivation:

The described functionality supports system designers in gaining confidence that no essential requirements are omitted ultimately facilitating the certification process. This is an ambitious goal since at this stage of the project we cannot say which of the regulatory requirements are amenable to formal verification. Ideally, this user story will lead to identifying a catalogue of formally verifiable regulatory requirements and their formulation in a suitable formal notation.

Building Blocks: A catalogue of requirements formulated in a way suitable for formal verification.

3.3 Model of ENTRUST Onboarding Phase – Refinement from the Reference Architecture

Figure 3.3.1: Enrolment Phase as defined in ENTRUST reference architecture

The aim of this phase of Task 3.1 is to refine and analyse the enrolment phase of the ENTRUST reference architecture introduced in D2.1. The Figure 3.3.1 shows a diagram representing the secure enrolment process of a CMD to the domain proposed in D2.1. To ensure that this process is secure we aim to formally verify the security requirements defined within ENTRUST using tools such as VerifPal [5].

The steps presented in the secure enrolment diagram need to be further refined to reach such a level of detail that would enable us to obtain a model of the entire process that can be fed to a formal verification tool. To have more manageable tasks, we decided to split the secure enrolment phase into two sub-phases. Figure 3.3.2 presents the two sub-phases. The first one represents the MUD flow and the authentication of the CMD to the Domain Manager (DM) with the goal of obtaining the Master Session Key (MSK) that is going to be used for deriving new service-specific keys used in the communication between the two components. Figure 3.3.2 highlights the steps that are included in the first sub-phase. The second sub-phase represents the steps required for the CMD to obtain the verifiable credentials.

Figure 3.3.2 - Sub-phases of the Enrolment

As can be seen in Figure 3.3.2., the enrolment diagram has a high level of abstraction. In order to model it, we need to expand each step of the flow. As mentioned, this sub-phase focuses on the MUD flow and authentication.

Several alternative solutions for device authentication were discussed among the project partners. We decided to use the Extensible Authentication Protocol (EAP) framework for the network access authentication. This framework is commonly used in wireless networks and provides support for multiple authentication methods [6]. More specifically, the EAP Pre-Shared Key (PSK) protocol is the method used for mutual authentication and session key derivation by making use of the pre-shared key installed by the manufacturer on the device [7]. In our approach, the EAP-PSK is executed in a delegated manner: the protocol parties are the CMD and the AAA (on the manufacturer site), but they communicate via the Domain Manager which delegates the received EAP-PSK messages. After successful authentication, both the CMD and the AAA obtain the MSK used for future secure communication. As the last step, the AAA securely transmits the MSK to the DM by using a pre-established secure channel.

It should be noted that the EAP-PSK protocol that is described in the next paragraphs is the original one. In the context of ENTRUST, which aims at the complete secure lifecycle

management of CMDs, this process departs by the onboarding of a device into the operational domain. Onboarding is about bootstrapping the trust in a CMD and, as such, ENTRUST aims at extending the EAP protocol by the ensurance of the fact that authentication and onboarding of a CMD is only possible if it can provide the proof of ownership of specific attributes. Nevertheless, we start by a detailed description of the EAP protocol and the process of its formal verification while aiming to be able to abstract this process and apply it to the extension of the EAP protocol that will take place in the project.

To make sure that the security requirements of a device are satisfied in our CMD network, an MUD file needs to be specified by the manufacturer and then processed by the domain manager. The goal of this file is to provide information related to access and network functionality they require to properly function [8]. To define the flow for the MUD file we used the proposed extended-MUD approach described in Chapter 5. The goal of this flow is to securely retrieve the MUD file, process it, and apply the requirements defined on the domain.

Figure 3.3.3 - Onboarding Phase

To model the onboarding phase, we start by creating a model diagram to provide a visual representation that aids in understanding, analysis, and communication with our partners to get relevant feedback throughout the entire modelling process. Additionally, a generic version of the model facilitates the translation of the model diagram to various verification tools in the future.

Figure 3.3.3 shows the model diagram of the MUD flow and authentication of the CMD which will be referred to as the *onboarding* phase that includes the bootstrapping and enrolment phases. Steps one to three represent the bootstrapping phase of the CMD during which the PSK and MUD files are installed on the CMD, and the MUD file is published on the MUD file server. These steps are executed by the manufacturer on its premises. The remaining steps are executed when the device is deployed in the actual domain (e.g. in a hospital setting). Steps 4 to 14 represent the

delegated authentication of the CMD to the domain network. The last steps, 15 to 18, are related to the processing of the MUD file by the DM.

The main goals of the onboarding phase are (i) to perform mutual authentication between the CMD and the AAA using the PSK; (ii) to obtain the MSK which is the outcome of the authentication using EAP-PSK protocol. Step 4 marks the initiation of the authentication by requesting the manufacturer authentication server (AAA server) its identity information ID_S, and a random challenge RAND_S. Then the DM forwards it to the CMD (steps 5 and 6). The CMD generates a random challenge RAND_P and computes the message authentication code (MAC) MAC_P based on its identity, RAND_P, and the information received from the AAA server in step 6. Furthermore, the MAC_P is sent to the DM and then delegated to the AAA server (steps 7 to 9). In this phase, the MAC_P is verified, the AAA server computes its MAC (MAC_S), derives the MSK, and the Transient EAP Key (TEK) based on the random number RAND_P and the Key-derivation Key (KDK). The TEK is then used to derive the tag for the protected channel. The goal of the protected channel exchange is to check if the CMD and AAA have derived the MSK and the ephemeral session key based on the shared initial key material (PSK). The MAC_S and the protected channel information are sent to the DM and forwarded to the CMD (steps 9 and 10), where the MAC_S is verified, then the MSK is derived by the CMD, and it sets up the protected channel. The tag of the protected channel is forwarded to the AAA server (steps 11 and 12) where it is verified. Finally, the MSK is encrypted by the AAA server and sent to the DM to be used for further communication between the CMD and the domain. For more details and sizes of the keys please refer to the EAP-PSK protocol [7]. The MSK is now shared between the CMD and DM and will be used for deriving additional key material used to access various services.

The next step of the onboarding phase is to process the MUD file. In steps 15 and 16, the DM requests the MUD Manager to retrieve the MUD file from the given URL. The MUD manager retrieves the file, extracts its policies, and applies them.

In the modelling process of the onboarding protocol, certain assumptions are made to make the verification process more manageable in the initial phase. Furthermore, this allows us to focus on key aspects and to obtain a more complete model. As the process of modelling and verification is iterative, we use these assumptions as a starting point for analysis that can be adjusted once we gain more knowledge of the system.

At the beginning of the onboarding phase, it is assumed that the PSK is securely installed on the CMD such that an attacker cannot get it, for example, in a TPM. An overview of all secure elements in ENTRUST is presented in deliverable D4.1. In addition, the certificate of the MUD file is generated to ensure the authenticity and integrity of the MUD. During the delegated authentication process, we assume that there is a trusted communication channel between the DM and the AAA server, thus, the MSK is not exposed to the attacker in step 13 where it is shared after successful authentication. The model intentionally does not specify how this secure communication channel is established. There are many possibilities for this, for example the RADIUS protocol.

The general assumption is that there are no attacks on the manufacturer and hospital premises to attempt the leak of the PSK. This is a general assumption that is made in all PSK scenarios. Moreover, the current onboarding protocol does not provide forward secrecy, the property that ensures that even if the attacker gains access to the key, it is not possible to decrypt past communication, this being an inherent issue for all PSK approaches.

Figure 3.3.4 - EAP-PSK Key Hierarchy

Figure 3.3.4 shows the key hierarchy in EAP-PSK as defined in the standard. The pre-shared key (PSK) is the initial keying material shared between the CMD and the AAA server. It is assumed that it is shared by at most one pair of CMD and AAA. Furthermore, we assume that the AAA server identifies the correct PSK per device based on the CMD identity. Both the device identity and the PSK for this device are set up in the manufacturer bootstrapping phase.

The PSK is used to derive two long-term keys to be used by the EAP-PSK protocol: Authentication Key (AK) and Key-derivation Key (KDK). This derivation is done once and the PSK is not used anymore. The standard specifies that the derivation is done using Modified Counter Mode (MCM). The size of keys and the concrete details of the used crypto algorithms can be obtained from the standard. The AK is used in the first two EAP-PSK messages to calculate the MACs. The KDK is used along with the RAND_P to generate the Transient EAP Key (TEK) and the Master Session Key (MSK). The TEK is used as a session key in the 3rd and 4th EAP-PSK messages where the protected channel is used. The MSK is the key material exported after the successful execution of the protocol. In our case, it is transported from the AAA server to the DM using key wrapping and is used in future communication. In this way, each pair of a CMD and DM share a unique MSK.

It should be noted that the figure omits the Extended MSK which is reserved for future use according to the EAP-PSK standard.

3.4 Security Requirements

The security goals of the onboarding phase are defined based on the security requirements described in D2.1. Security requirement SR_7 states that all communications of CMD should be authenticated, therefore, during the onboarding phase, we aim to obtain mutual authentication between the CMD and DM. Mutual authentication guarantees that both the CMD and the DM authenticate each other simultaneously. This means that both parties verify the identity of the other, preventing any potential attacker from impersonating either the CMD or the DM and sending messages on their behalf.

Security requirement SR_18 requires secure cryptographic key management which relates to the confidentiality of the cryptographic keys used within the onboarding phase. The confidentiality property ensures that an attacker cannot obtain a private key explicitly or in terms of its components. As a rule of thumb in cryptography, there needs to be a strict separation of keys per function. Hence, the EAP-PSK protocol achieves that by making use of separated sub-keys for mutual authentication and session key derivation, using the PSK to only derive the AK and KDK.

Furthermore, requirement SR_8 aims to ensure data integrity, protecting the integrity of the data against unwanted modification. The EAP-PSK protocol employed in the onboarding phase provides integrity protection thanks to the tag of its protected channel. This tag is a Message Authentication Code (MAC) that has the purpose of providing assurances regarding the integrity and the source of the message. For more information related to data integrity refer to the EAP-PSK Protocol [7].

To express these security requirements more specifically to the onboarding phase, we need to ensure that the CMD and the AAA server authenticate with each other, and the MAC is verified throughout the entire process. Moreover, the confidentiality of the following keys needs to be guaranteed: MSK, KDK, AK, and TEK.

3.5 Adversarial Model

We consider an active attacker model in which the attacker can intercept, modify, delete, and inject messages allowing for a thorough analysis of our protocol. This corresponds to the Dolev-Yao model used in symbolic analysis of protocols (see Section 3.6 for further explanation). The active attacker model opens possibilities for well-known attacks like replay and man-in-the-middle (MITM).

Taking into consideration replay attacks and MITM attacks, the EAP-PSK protocol provides protection against replay attacks for its mutual authentication due to the use of the random numbers RAND_S and RAND_P that would require 2^{64} successful authentications before it can be replayed. Furthermore, the use of a nonce for each message of the protocol ensures replay protection during the conversation of the protected channel. The keys derived during the authentication process are unique to the client-server pair which makes the potentially intercepted data difficult to interpret. Moreover, the cryptographic mechanism employed includes integrity checks, making it challenging to tamper with or forge the messages without knowing the PSK, thus, providing protection against MITM attacks.

Furthermore, we need to take into account various scenarios to model the attacker's behaviour. By considering the standard practice in security, we have a scenario where the attacker tries to retrieve the PSK on the manufacturer's premises, during the provision of key for the device. This scenario would not be possible because we assume during the modelling process that there are no attacks on the manufacturer and hospital premises. Furthermore, this assumption prevents a similar scenario where the attacker tries to leak the PSK on the hospital's premises.

Another scenario relevant to the adversarial model is when a malicious device controlled by an attacker tries to execute the onboarding process to the DM. Given that the PSK cannot be leaked from either the DM or the manufacturer, the malicious device would not have a valid PSK to authenticate to the AAA server. Thus, the onboarding attempt would be unsuccessful. Another scenario in this line is when an attacker tries to onboard a well-behaving CMD to a controlled (malicious) DM with the goal to onboard a device to an untrusted domain. To succeed in this attempt, the attacker must be able to establish a trusted connection between the DM and the manufacturer's AAA which is prevented by one of the assumptions mentioned above.

3.6 Overview of Tool-assisted Security Protocol Verification

Communication protocols play a key role in satisfying the security requirements of distributed systems. The two main ingredients of such protocols are the used security and cryptographic primitives (e.g. types of keys) and the intended behaviour of the involved communicating parties. Both are crucial in achieving properties like confidentiality, integrity, authenticity, forward secrecy, and others. Proving rigorously that a protocol satisfies such properties is a non-trivial task. Protocols that at first glance look simple and robust may have flaws that are difficult to find by a manual inspection. A notorious example is the classical Needham-Schroeder protocols where vulnerabilities were discovered more than 15 years after their introduction. These vulnerabilities (namely the replay and man-in-the-middle attacks) were found after the protocols were modelled and checked by generic model checking tools.

A significant amount of research was devoted to modelling and automatic analysis of security protocols. The tools that support this task take into account the specifics of the security properties to be checked and are based on techniques from formal verification like model checking and theorem proving. The contemporary security protocol analysis tools can be classified into two groups based on the level of abstraction in specifying the protocol. We distinguish between *symbolic* and *computational* security analysis.

The symbolic security analysis (aka *symbolic* model or *Dolev-Yao* model) specifies protocols in an abstract way. The participants of the protocol are modelled as abstract machines (processes) that can exchange messages. The messages are algebraic terms. Cryptographic primitives are modelled algebraically based on equational theories. The adversary can observe, record, manipulate, create, and inject messages. This model assumes perfect cryptography, that is, the attacker can perform cryptographic operations only if it possesses the required cryptographic keys.

The symbolic model, even though idealized, allows easier analysis and is suitable to show that the protocol is broken under the given assumptions. The two most mature tools based on the symbolic model are ProVerif [9] and Tamarin [10].

ProVerif specifies the behaviour of the participants in applied pi-calculus where the exchanged messages are algebraic terms. The most commonly supported properties that can be checked are *reachability* (used to check secrecy), *correspondence* (used to check authenticity), and to a lesser extent *behaviour equivalence* on different protocol runs. Internally ProVerif works similarly to a theorem prover. The processes in pi-calculus are translated to Horn clauses and the tool's algorithm tries to prove the properties assuming unbounded number of sessions (protocol runs). The attempt to prove a given property can produce three outcomes: property is proven, property does not hold, or no result is produced (*do not know* outcome, the check does not terminate). In the second case, ProVerif produces a trace with a protocol run that shows an attack. Lack of termination is a possible outcome due to the complexity of the protocol and the underlying proof procedure which is generally undecidable on unbounded number of sessions and inputs.

Tamarin specifies the protocol in terms of multi-set rewriting rules and as such belongs to the larger family of tools based on rewriting logic. The properties are specified as formulas in a fragment of First-Order Logic (FOL) and are checked on the traces derived from the protocol runs. Cryptographic primitives are, similar to ProVerif, specified in equational theories. Internally Tamarin uses a constraints-solving algorithm for falsification and verification of properties assuming unbounded number of sessions. Like in ProVerif, non-termination is a possible outcome.

Both Tamarin and ProVerif pose challenges in learning and mastering their specification languages which in the behavioural part are rather different. Security protocol engineers tend to

think in terms of sequences of messages exchanged among the protocol participants (the familiar Alice-Bob notation) and to specify the content of the messages based on a set of well-known cryptographic functions (hash and key derivation functions, symmetric encryption, etc.). Translating these concepts to the specification language of a tool is not always straightforward.

VerifPal [5] is a relatively recent tool inspired by ProVerif and working in the symbolic model. It is created with the main aim to provide simpler syntax that closely resembles the Alice-Bob notation. It also provides the most used crypto primitives as first-class language constructs. Its inner workings resemble those of ProVerif.

DeepSec [11] is a verification tool that allows checking security properties expressed as *trace equivalence*. Trace equivalence means that an attacker is unable to distinguish two distinct systems only based on the messages observed after interacting with them. This is useful, for example, in e-voting systems but it is still unclear if this feature is relevant in the context of ENTRUST security properties.

As can be seen from the discussion above, each tool has strengths and weaknesses and very often the security engineers need to use more than one tool to check the complete set of security properties. This comes with the price of learning several potentially rather diverse specification languages. SAPIC+ [12] aims at mitigating this problem by providing a single front-end process calculus syntax and translations to Tamarin, ProVerif and DeepSec. If a translation to more than one tool is possible, they can run in parallel to check the given property.

The *computational security analysis* (aka protocol analysis in the *computational model*) specifies protocols in a more concrete way compared to the symbolic model. Messages are represented as bitstrings, the cryptographic primitives are functions on these bitstrings. Adversaries are probabilistic Turing machines capable of running polynomial time algorithms. Security requirements are formulated as the probability for the adversary to achieve a certain goal. In order to satisfy a requirement, this probability has to be negligible. In contrast to the symbolic model, the length of bitstrings and keys play a role. The two main analysis methods are game-based and simulation-based experiments.

The computational model is considered to be more realistic, but the proofs are more complicated and more difficult to automate in a tool. An example of a tool that works in the computational model is CryptoVerif [13]. It constructs game-based proofs of concrete security properties. Its specification language is similar to the one of ProVerif.

In this task, we opt for modelling and analysis of protocols in the symbolic model since this approach is more amenable to automation and provides several mature tools. The current choice of tool is VerifPal due to the simplicity of its syntax and the very compact and straightforward representation of the properties to be checked.

3.7 Modelling the Onboarding Phase with VerifPal: Model and Requirements

3.7.1 The VerifPal Language

VerifPal provides textual concrete syntax that closely resembles the Alice-Bob notation. Every model in VerifPal starts with a declaration of the assumptions about the attacker. Attacker may be *active* or *passive*. An active attacker can intercept, record, delete, insert, and modify messages. A passive attacker can only observe and record messages.

The participants in the protocol are called *principals* of the protocol. They can create values out of primitives and crypto functions and can send these values in messages to other principals transmitted in an open channel. The following is a simple example of a protocol in VerifPal.


```

attacker[active]
principal A [
    knows private k
    generates payload
    m = MAC(k, payload)
]
principal B[
    knows private k
]
A -> B: m, payload
principal B[
    _ = ASSERT(MAC(k, payload), m)?
    generates payload1
    m1 = ENC(k, payload1)
]
B -> A: m1
principal A[
    m1_dec = DEC(k, m1)
]
queries[
    confidentiality? k
    confidentiality? payload1
    authentication? A -> B: m
]

```

The two principals *A* and *B* share a symmetric key *k*, known only to them. This is indicated with the declarations 'knows private *k*'. *A* generates a random value *payload*, calculates the message authentication code (MAC) *m* for it using the key *k*, and then sends the code and the payload to *B*. Observe that the MAC function is a built-in primitive in VerifPal. *B* calculates the MAC of the received payload and compares it to the received value *m*. This is done by using the ASSERT primitive that can fail if the two values are not equal. If the check fails, then the protocol run is aborted. If it passes, *B* can be certain about the authenticity of the message as coming from *A* since the assumption is that only *A* knows the shared secret key *k*. In the remaining steps, *B* generates the value *payload1* and encrypts it with *k*, then sends the encrypted message *m1* to *A*. *A* uses the shared key to decrypt the message. Observe here two other built-in primitives that denote symmetric encryption and decryption: ENC and DEC. Apart from these primitives, VerifPal also provides key derivation, hash, and asymmetric encryption functions among others.

An important part of the VerifPal model is the *queries* section that contains the properties to be verified. The first two queries check if the values *k* and *payload1* can be known to the attacker. The third one checks for authentication of *A* to *B* by sending the message *m*. The check succeeds if the verifier concludes that it is only *A* that can send the message *m* to *B* (*A* cannot be impersonated). Apart from these queries, VerifPal supports also checks for freshness of values in different protocol runs, unlikability, and equivalence. Basic forward secrecy can be analysed using *phases* (not illustrated here).

As can be seen, VerifPal provides an intuitive and compact syntax for the protocol steps and the queries along with a rich set of built-in crypto primitives that hides the underlying algebraic semantics. However, as the authors of the tool admit, VerifPal is not as powerful as Tamarin or ProVerif and may be insufficient for more complex protocols and queries.

3.7.2 Model of the Onboarding Phase

The model of the onboarding phase in VerifPal is given in [Appendix 1](#). Only the steps that involve the mutual authentication, derivation of key material and that contribute to the security requirements are modelled. The model, therefore, covers steps 6-13, which in essence capture the delegated authentication based on EAP-PSK. It does not cover the MUD flow which will be modelled and verified as a next step.

The EAP-PSK standard mandates that the PSK is used exactly once to derive the authentication key (AK) and the key-derivation key (KDK) by both the CMD and AAA. This is done using Modified Counter Mode. There is no primitive in VerifPal that represents MCM so for simplicity the initial PSK is not defined in the model. Instead, we assume that the AK and KDK are already derived and known to CMD and AAA as shared secrets.

The following fragment shows the declarations of the CMD, AAA and DM in the model:

```
principal Cmd[
  knows private id_p // CMD identifier
  knows private kdk // key derivation key
  knows private ak // authentication key
  generates rand_p
]

principal Aaa[
  knows private id_s // AAA identifier
  knows private kdk // key derivation key
  knows private ak // authentication key
  knows private k // encryption key
  generates rand_s
]

principal Dm[
  knows private k // encryption key
]
```

Observe that the identifiers of CMD and AAA are defined as private values which in the later steps will be send in messages. Furthermore, AAA and DM share a key k which will be used to transport the MSK derived by AAA to DM. As already explained, this is an assumption; how k is obtained is not modelled.

Steps 5 and 6 show the first EAP-PSK message and its forwarding to the CMD. The CMD then calculates the MAC based on the two identifiers, and the two random numbers:

```
// Step 5: Send identity
Aaa -> Dm: id_s, rand_s

// Step 6: Request identity
Dm -> Cmd: id_s, rand_s

principal Cmd[
  // Compute MAC_P
  mac_p = MAC(ak, CONCAT(id_p, rand_p, id_s, rand_s))
]

// Step 7: Response Identity
```



```
Cmd -> Dm: rand_p, id_p, mac_p
```

In step 7, the second EAP-PSK message is initiated. Note that this step differs slightly from the standard: *rand_s* is not sent in this message. This is due to a VerifPal constraint that prohibits sending values that are already known to the recipient (*rand_s* is known to DM and AAA).

The DM then will forward the message to AAA which in turn will perform validation of the *mac_p*:

```
principal Aaa[
  // Verify MAC_P
  _ = ASSERT(MAC(ak, CONCAT(id_p, rand_p, id_s, rand_s)), mac_p)?

  // derive transient key for the protected channel and MSK
  eap_session_key_aaa, msk_aaa = HKDF(rand_p, kdk, nil)

  // Compute MAC_S
  mac_s = MAC(ak, CONCAT(id_s, rand_p))

  // Protected channel
  generates payload
  tag = MAC(eap_session_key_aaa, CONCAT(payload, rand_s))
]
```

If the *mac_p* validation succeeds (see the ASSERT check), the AAA successfully authenticates the CMD based on the possession of the shared *ak*. It should be noted that the model omits the identification of the proper *ak* to be used by the AAA based on the supplied identifier *id_p*. As a next action, AAA derives the TEK (*eap_session_key_aaa* in the model) and the MSK (*msk_aaa*) using the VerifPal HKDF primitive for key derivation. It takes as arguments *kdk* and *rand_p* as prescribed by the standard. *mac_s* is computed and will be used by the CMD to authenticate AAA. The last two actions performed by AAA are to establish the protected channel. They do not follow the protocol as defined in the standard since VerifPal does not have primitives for working with numbers (so message sequence numbers cannot be modelled). The goal is to demonstrate that at least the session key TEK has been derived. The payload is generated randomly (in the standard it is the indication of the authentication result), the tag is computed as the MAC of the payload and the *rand_s* and then the payload, and the two MACs are sent to DM which forwards the message to CMD.

```
// Step 10: Request protected channel
Dm -> Cmd: mac_s, payload, tag

principal Cmd[
  // Verify MAC_S
  _ = ASSERT(MAC(ak, CONCAT(id_s, rand_p)), mac_s)?

  // derive transient key for the protected channel and MSK
  eap_session_key_cmd, msk_cmd = HKDF(rand_p, kdk, nil)

  // Verify tag of the protected channel
  _ = ASSERT(MAC(eap_session_key_cmd, CONCAT(payload, rand_s)), tag)?

  // Protected channel
  generates payload1
  tag1 = MAC(eap_session_key_cmd, CONCAT(payload1, rand_s))
]
```


]

Upon receiving the message, the CMD first checks the validity of *mac_s* using *ak* and only if this check succeeds it derives its own TEK and MSK. It then verifies the tag using the derived *eap_session_key_cmd*, generates the payload for the last EAP-PSK message (*payload1*) and computes *tag1* using the TEK *eap_session_key_cmd*. With this value, the CMD can send the last EAP-PSK message.

Finally, we discuss the actions of the AAA in the last steps of the model.

```
principal Aaa[
  // Verify tag of the protected channel tag
  _ = ASSERT(MAC(eap_session_key_aaa, CONCAT(payload1, rand_s)), tag1)?

  // Encrypt MSK
  msk_enc = ENC(k, msk_aaa)
]

// Step 13: Delegation response MSK
Aaa -> Dm: msk_enc

principal Dm[
  // Decrypt MSK
  msk_dm = DEC(k, msk_enc)
]
```

It first verifies the received *tag1* using its own already derived TEK. Then it exports the MSK *msk_aaa* by encrypting it with *k* (shared with DM). The DM decrypts the received MSK. From now on, the CMD and the DM share the MSK that can be used for deriving further keys that protect communication with various services.

The queries in the model reflect the security requirements of the model: confidentiality of the keys *ak*, *kdk*, *msk_aaa*, the two TEKs, and the mutual authentication between CMD and AAA.

```
queries[
  confidentiality? msk_aaa
  confidentiality? eap_session_key_cmd
  confidentiality? eap_session_key_aaa
  confidentiality? ak
  confidentiality? kdk
  authentication? Dm -> Cmd: mac_s
  authentication? Dm -> Aaa: mac_p
]
```

Here the semantics of authentication is that, for example, only DM can send the value *mac_s* to CMD, which in turn has received it from AAA. The same query is applied to check the authentication of CMD to AAA.

We do not check for any forward secrecy, that is, how the communication is affected if a long-term key is leaked (e.g. *ak*). In VerifPal this can be modelled using *phases*. Phases allow a protocol specification to be decomposed sequentially in parts, each part is called a *phase*. Each phase can be verified separately, and it is possible to state that certain information (e.g. a key) is leaked after a given phase thus affecting the verification of the next phase. It is already known

that EAP-PSK does not provide perfect forward secrecy. Compromise of the PSK leads to compromise of the recorded past sessions and compromise of the future sessions (the adversary is capable of impersonating both parties).

The described model will be verified under the symbolic model. We do not provide any analysis under the computational model. It is known that an earlier protocol named AKEP2 has been proven as secure in the computational model [14]. The mutual authentication mechanism of EAP-PSK is inspired by AKEP2 and uses the same first 2 steps thus the results in [14] can be considered valid in this context as well.

3.8 Verification Results

To verify the onboarding protocol, we are using the VerifPal model described in Section 3.7. In order to run the verification for this model, we used the High Performance Computing services provided by the Eindhoven University of Technology so we could run the verification for a longer period without interruption. Based on the experience with tool-based protocol verification reported in the literature, we decided on a time limit of 48 hours. If the verification does not end within this limit, then a different approach needs to be employed to verify the security of the onboarding protocol.

The verification of the VerifPal model did not finish within 48 hours. As abstracting the behaviour for modelling protocols is a common practice, we decided to abstract some of the steps in our protocol. First, we removed the check of the tags of the protected channels, we ran the model again, and it still did not finish. Then, we removed the protected channel step, so we do not derive the TEK anymore, but the verification did not finish either. When we also removed the provisioning of the MSK to the DM, the verification finished in a relatively short time, and we obtained a positive result.

We investigated what might be the problem and we changed the HKDF function that derives the TEK and the MSK to a HASH function. We also included the provisioning of the MSK to the DM in the final step. The verification finished successfully and the security requirements we were verifying hold. At this step, we are still missing the setup of the protected channel. Thus, we update the model to include the derivation of the TEK to set up the protected channel and run the verification of the model. Unfortunately, the verification process did not finish in 48 hours.

To conclude, it appears that VerifPal might not be able to handle the verification of our model in a reasonable time. We have also tried to run some of the examples provided in the VerifPal distribution, but the verification did not finish within 48 hours either. Therefore, we change our approach and use a different tool to verify the onboarding phase.

We decided to use ProVerif to verify our model. While VerifPal uses a high-level language for specifying protocols, ProVerif uses a more formal language based on applied pi-calculus. In order to convert our model to ProVerif, we manually rewrite the VerifPal model to ProVerif by translating the high-level descriptions, roles, and interactions into the formal language of ProVerif. The main difference is that we need to define in more detail the processes, channels, and how entities interact. In addition to that, all crypto primitives must be explicitly defined as equational theories. After we obtained the ProVerif model of the onboarding phase, we ran it using the online tool provided by their developers and we received a positive result in just a few seconds, confirming that our protocol fulfils the defined security requirements. The ProVerif code is given in [Appendix 8.3](#). The code is not explained in this deliverable, this is left as future work.

3.9 Functional Specifications for Formal Verification

Table 1: User Stories for Formal Verification

ID#	User story	I want to <Action>	So that <Reason>	Description
FV_1	Formal verification of secure device onboarding	As a DM, I want to formally verify the security requirements for the device onboarding phase.	Only trusted devices can join the domain	Domain administrators formally verify the security requirements to ensure that only trusted devices join their network.
FV_2	Formal verification of secure communication	As DM, I want to formally verify that secure communication channels are established.	The enrolled devices can securely communicate within the domain	The domain administrator formally verifies the requirements of secure communication to ensure that devices to securely communicate within the network.
FV_3	Formal verification of secure software updates	As DM, I want to formally verify the security requirements for the software updates phase.	New updates are not compromised during the transmission and installation process	Domain administrators formally verify the security requirements for the software update phase so that the updates are not compromised during the transmission and installation process.
FV_4	Formal verification of remote attestation protocol	As manufacturer, I want to formally verify the remote attestation protocol	Every device can do remote attestation	Manufacturers formally verify the remote attestation protocol to ensure that every device can do secure remote attestation.
FV_5	Formal verification of delegated authentication and secure MUD provision	As manufacturer, I want to formally verify the delegated authentication and MUD provision	The AAA server can authenticate a device during the onboarding.	The manufacturer formally verifies the delegated authentication and MUD provision so that the devices are securely authenticated to the AAA server during the onboarding phase.
FV_6	Formal verification of secure software update	As manufacturer, I want to formally verify the security requirements for the software updates phase.	The device is not compromised during the update phase.	Manufacturers formally verify the security requirements for the software update phase so that the updates are not compromised during the transmission and installation process.
FV_7	Define new protocols	As manufacturer, I want to define new protocols in an abstract way.	The protocols can be verified.	The behaviour and the cryptographic primitives used are explicitly defined at a level of details that allows verification and implementation. (such a way that could fulfil new requirements)
FV_8	Specify security properties	As manufacturer, I want to specify security properties in an abstract way by providing a user-friendly platform to engineers without formal verification background.	The requirements can be verified against the model	The manufacturer can specify the security requirements in a way that does not require expert knowledge in the used verification tools.

ID#	User story	I want to <Action>	So that <Reason>	Description
FV_9	Verify security requirements	As manufacturer, I want to verify the security requirements by using state-of-the-art verification tools in a transparent way, possibly by automatically generating specification in a given language from the defined model.	The manufacturer engineers do not need expert-level knowledge of verification tools	The engineers can use an abstract way to verify the security requirements by making use of multiple state-of-the-art verification tools.

3.10 Conclusions and Next Steps

We took the first steps to define a refined model of the ENTRUST onboarding phase that allows formal modelling and verification of its security requirements. As proposed in the ENTRUST reference architecture it is based on delegated pre-shared key mutual authentication mechanism inspired by the EAP-PSK standard.

In this chapter we provided a brief overview of the approaches for verification of security protocols and their associated tools. The onboarding phase was modelled and analysed following the symbolic security model approach.

We first applied the VerifPal language and tool due to its simple and intuitive syntax and its accessibility for security engineers that may not have experience with more complex formal notations like pi-calculus and rewriting logic. Unfortunately, the full model was not successfully verified after running for 48 hours. A simplified version that covers the mutual authentication steps was successfully verified. As an alternative, we encoded the model in the language of ProVerif and showed that all security properties can be verified and are fulfilled.

The envisaged next steps span several directions:

- Extending the onboarding phase model to include more attributes unique to the device being onboarded and checking the authenticity of the MUD
- Modelling and verification of other aspects of the device behaviour, for example, secure communication during operation, secure usage of services, secure software update
- Modelling and verification with different tools. In this deliverable we shared our experience with VerifPal and took initial steps using ProVerif. In the future we will focus on two tools: ProVerif and Tamarin
- An interesting research direction that can be explored if time permits is to design a tool-independent notation for protocol specification that acts as a front-end for several protocol verification tools
- In case the verification of a property does not converge within reasonable time, it can be verified over observations collected at runtime. The identification of such properties and the required information for their checks is a matter of future work

4 Threat Modelling and Software Verification

The role of threat modelling is to identify known threats for a specific type of device. Current threat modelling tools can be divided using two main characteristics: automation level, such as tools that are manual or tools that can be highly automated, and the way that the output is given, be it in a graphical, user friendly way, or a more formal, machine friendly way [15]. Tools that are user friendly tend to be manual, while tools that are giving outputs that can be easily processed by other computer systems, tend to be automated. The Threat Modelling module of ENTRUST is leveraging a large language model, to create user friendly outputs, while also being able to put it in a format that can be easily processed by other systems, via systemic identifiers. This module will communicate with Risk Assessment module during the pre-deployment phase, by feeding to it data regarding threat vectors for a specific device.

Software verification has the role of checking if an application adheres to a set of requirements. Current Static Application Security Testing (SAST) tools capable of doing verification of the source code to search for known security issues [16]. A problem that arises from this is that 3rd party modules, such as libraries, can still be infected with malicious code, that can compromise a software product. The Software Verification module of ENTRUST allows for the verification of such modules, by scanning them for malicious patterns. Moreover, ENTRUST module can be easily integrated into a DevOps pipeline, enabling an easier and more secure workflow. This module will help developers during the pre-deployment phase of CMDs to detect issues regarding the software products they are working on, such as firmware or user applications.

4.1 Objectives and Context

Within the scope of the ENTRUST project, the objectives related to threat modelling and software verification for connected medical devices are defined to address the unique challenges posed by the healthcare sector's increasing reliance on technology. These objectives focus on ensuring the security and integrity of connected medical devices which are critical to patient care and sensitive data protection.

The primary objective of threat modelling within the scope of the ENTRUST project is to develop a robust framework capable of generating comprehensive threat landscapes tailored to specific medical devices. This framework is designed to not only identify potential vulnerabilities but also to construct attack scenarios, which are then evaluated by the risk assessment module for appropriate mitigation strategies. A critical aspect of this objective is the in-house processing of threat modelling to ensure that sensitive data remains within the controlled environment, eliminating the exposure to 3rd party entities.

In the realm of software verification, the main goal is to establish a rigorous testing protocol for software developed within the healthcare industry. This involves verifying the integrity and security of the software that operates on medical devices including the 3rd party binaries used along the workflow to ensure that the whole system is safe.

4.2 Engineering Stories

4.2.1 Threat Modelling & Risk Assessment

STORY-I: As a security administrator, I want to be able to have an up-to-date view of the entire topology of the services graph chain.

Objective: To achieve one of the main motivations behind ENTRUST, the measurement of the trustworthiness level of CMDs, one requirement is to have a realist threat landscape, based on which to assess the risk of each device. This threat landscape should include the latest found vulnerabilities, so the security administrator can create a security strategy to mitigate them. At

first, a collection regarding threat intelligence is done, in a manner that allows for integration with other tools. Afterwards, the intelligence is done to compute the risk and to keep track of all network services.

Motivation: To satisfy this need, ENTRUST offers a solution that is divided into two different tools. During the pre-deployment phase, threat modelling module, is searching for known security issues and creates attack scenarios. This is then put into a package that can be easily processed by other machines, such as JSON, and is fed into the risk assessment module. This way, we can identify vulnerabilities and secure the network during the designing phase. This allows for a more efficient identification of vulnerabilities and a lower cost of fixing them.

Building Blocks: The two main building blocks for this is the threat modelling and risk assessment module. Threat modelling is scanning for new vulnerabilities in established databases, such as NIST NVD, and creates a systematic way of identification of attacks by mapping information between multiple knowledge bases, such as MITRE CWE. To create a user-friendly way of presenting these vulnerabilities, it's using a LLM to create attack scenarios, so the security administrator will have a better overview regarding each vulnerability that has been found. This is then saved as a JSON that is served to the risk assessment module to compute and keep track of the risk of a specific device that is used in the network.

STORY-II: As a Service Provider, I want to be able to compare the ATL with the RTL for a specific node or data item as part of the overall service graph chain.

Objective: As aforementioned, one core motivation behind the design of the ENTRUST framework is the monitoring and maintenance of the trustworthiness level of Connected Medical Devices belonging to a service graph chain. The approach followed in this regard is the evaluation of the Required Trust Level of the device based on available information on the most prominent threats and vulnerabilities affecting this type of device, and the calculation of the Actual Trust Level of the device based on the attestation of a set of trust properties. Thus, the RTL of the device is determined based on all types of identified attack vectors for the specified type of device, as well as the evaluation of their impact per trust property (e.g., a specific attack vector may have a lower impact when assessing the privacy of an attribute, but may impose a critical risk when it comes to security), considering the CMD both as an isolated entity, and as a part of the overall infrastructure it operates within.

Motivation: ENTRUST offers a wide array of tools and security enablers that support the aforementioned approach. For instance, for the calculation of the RTL, the Threat Modelling component is able to identify threats and vulnerabilities affecting each type of device based on existing databases and repositories, while the Digital Twin is able to assess and provide information regarding the likelihood and potential impact of the identified threats. Conversely, the remote attestation schemes of ENTRUST, such as Configuration Integrity Verification and Swarm Attestation are able to attest to the correctness of a set of trust properties based on information collected by the runtime monitoring and tracing capabilities of the device, and modules such as the Digital Twin and the Misbehaviour Detection component are able to provide updated information regarding newly identified threats and vulnerabilities. ENTRUST aims to place all the aforementioned components as part of a holistic framework that is able to ensure the trustworthiness of a CMD operating within a medical organization.

Building Blocks: The RTL for a CMD is calculated by the Risk Assessment engine, first during the design phase based on information available on the device in isolation, and is updated after the device is deployed to the target domain. Afterwards during runtime, the Trust Assessment

Framework is responsible for calculating the ATL based on the specified set of properties and the collected evidence. The Trust Decision Engine (TDE) is the component of the TAF which is responsible for performing the final step of the Trust Assessment process before a decision is made on whether the CMD can be considered to be in a trustworthy state, or if further action is needed in order to ensure its trustworthiness. The TDE either forwards the ATL calculated by the TLEE back to the Trust Controls component, or outputs a Trust Decision (TD). A TD is created after comparing the ATL to the RTL of the device based on the output of an attestation process on a set of trust properties. Whether the output of the TAF is an ATL or a TD depends on the needs of the application.

STORY-III: As a security administrator, I want to be able to fuse the output of various risk assessment methodologies, tailored to different trust properties of a system.

Objective: One of the core objectives of ENTRUST is to provide operational assurance to various types of CMDs operating within different types of medical organizations. One of the core components of this process is the Risk Assessment component, which is responsible for quantifying the risks affecting those CMDs, both as isolated devices, and as parts of a medical organization. In this regard, it should be noted that there are various risk assessment methodologies in the literature, which may be appropriate for different application domains. Therefore, the Risk Assessment methodology should provide the capability to consider the methodology (or methodologies) which are the most appropriate for the type of device or organization considered in each case.

Motivation: The Risk Assessment module needs to be designed in a modular manner that enables the integration of multiple methodologies. Taken one step further, the Risk Assessment approach of ENTRUST should enable merging and consolidating the outputs from different methodologies into a singular Risk Assessment outcome, by leveraging and integrating different types of methodologies. Recall that there are different trust properties that need to be considered as part of ENTRUST. Considering the above, it is possible that each methodology may be more appropriate for a specific type of property, such as security, safety, and privacy.

Building Blocks: Essentially, a two-step risk assessment approach is required: (i) At the first step, the risk assessment and quantification of each methodology is performed separately, and (ii) at the second step the outcomes of these methodologies are correctly fused in order to improve the accuracy of the risk assessment. Note that ENTRUST adopts the CVSS v3.1 methodology for quantification of the impact of vulnerabilities as the most appropriate metric for the target domain. However, in order to achieve backwards compatibility, CVSS v2 is also supported, and the possibility to integrate additional methodologies is considered.

4.2.2 Trust Assessment

STORY-I: As a Service Provider, I want to improve the safety and reliability of my functions through dynamic trust assessments on the operation of each medical device.

Objective: In order to be able to improve the safety and reliability of the CMDs operating in the context of a medical organization or hospital, a method is required for the assessing the level of trustworthiness of the device and evaluating whether it can be considered to be in a trustworthy state. To this end, the approach followed by ENTRUST entails the calculation of the Actual Trust Level of the device based on a set of trust properties, and comparing it to the Required Trust Level of the device, which is calculated based on available information on the type of device, as well as the types of threats and vulnerabilities affecting such devices. This user story entails the methodologies employed in order to calculate the ATL of the device during runtime, which will afterwards be used in order to evaluate whether mitigation actions are needed in order to bring the trustworthiness of the device to acceptable levels.

Motivation: Recall that, in the context of ENTRUST, multiple trust sources are considered for each device, based on which the trustworthiness of the device is evaluated. In order to evaluate the trustworthiness of a device, multiple attributes or properties need to be attested, which are specified in the Protection Profile of the device, and each attribute can be attested based on specific types of attestation evidence. This evidence is collected using the monitoring capabilities of the device, and is used by the runtime attestation schemes of the ENTRUST framework. Thus, ENTRUST needs to implement and integrate a Trust Assessment Framework which is able to evaluate trust sources for trustworthiness evidence, and evaluate propositions within the trust model in order to obtain their ATLs.

Building Blocks: Following an attestation process, it should be determined whether further actions need to be taken. Thus, a Trust Assessment process needs to be performed in order to calculate the ATL based on the attested properties. This process is handled by the Trust Assessment component, which contains a set of building blocks based on which the ATL is calculated: (i) the Request Manager which receives and manages requests for trust assessments, (ii) the Trust Model Manager (TMM) which locates the appropriate trust model(s), (iii) the Trust Source Manager which manages the sources of trust information based on the properties that can be attested by the monitoring mechanisms of the device, (iv) the Trustworthiness Level Expression Engine which applies the actual logic of the trust assessment methodology, and (v) the Trust Decision Engine which is responsible for comparing the calculated ATL to the RTL of the device.

STORY-II: As a security administrator, I want to be able to extract observations about a device's behaviour combining various trust sources.

Objective: Recall that each CMD is characterized by a set of attributes that can be used in order to verify its trustworthiness state, as well as the types of evidence that can be used in order to attest to the correctness of these attributes. Note that these attributes are specified in the Protection Profile of the device, including the types of attestation challenges which are appropriate for attesting to their correctness. The Trust Assessment component needs to be able to provide a Trust Assessment that consumes the various types of attribute attestations. This may include the remote attestation schemes provided by ENTRUST, such as Configuration Integrity Verification and Swarm Attestation, which utilize information collected by the monitoring and tracing capabilities of the device as attestation evidence. It may also include information from other trust sources, such as the network monitoring and AI-based Misbehaviour Detection system of ENTRUST.

Motivation: The service graph chain of a medical organization consists of multiple CMDs (referred to as trust objects in the context of Trust Assessment), between which various types of trust relationships are defined. This structure is represented through Trust Models (TM), which are graph-based models which contain all components and data needed to perform a certain function. TMs consist of trust objects and directional trust relationships between trust objects, and store trust sources used in order to quantify trust relationships. The TM is a core aspect of the Trust Assessment methodology to be used by the ENTRUST TAF, as it is the core input and provides the basis for the actual Trust Assessment logic employed by the TLEE. Since ENTRUST needs to capture various types of CMDs to be used in diverse medical organization environments, the employed TMs need to be generic enough to capture a broad choice of trust sources and trust relationships, so that it can adapt to the structure of the target organization.

Building Blocks: Recall that, following an attestation operation, the Trust Assessment Framework (TAF) of ENTRUST is responsible for the calculation of the ATL of the device, based

on the specified set of attributes. To this end, the TAF receives information regarding the Trust Model corresponding to the attested properties, the proposition pointing to the data whose trustworthiness should be attested, and the RTL against which the ATL needs to be compared. The Trust Model Manager (TMM) is responsible for locating the appropriate Trust Model, which is then forwarded to the TLEE in order to produce the ATL of the device.

STORY-III: As a Service Provider or Security Administrator, I want to be able to build my service exploiting a consolidated view of a medical service graph comprising trustworthy SW/HW functional assets.

Objective: As previously outlined, after an attestation operation is performed, a Trust Assessment process needs to be executed by the TAF in order to calculate the ATL of the attested properties, so that it can afterwards be compared to the RTL and it can be determined whether further actions need to be taken (such as the deployment of a secure software/firmware update or the addition of a new attestation action to the Protection Profile of the device). Thus, the Trust Assessment process needs to be positioned within the ENTRUST framework in a manner that enables the runtime provision of operational assurance for all devices in the Service Graph Chain, and to run continuous Trust Assessment operations and calculate trust opinions based on the attestation results received (or any other trust sources other than attestation operations). This approach serves towards the overall approach followed by ENTRUST with regard to the maintenance of the trust level of CMDs belonging to a medical organization. Note that this approach entails (i) the calculation of the RTL of the device, which is initially determined for the device in isolation (i.e., before it is deployed to the actual domain infrastructure) based on information regarding the type of device and known threats and vulnerabilities, and afterwards updated depending on information acquired by the various components of ENTRUST (e.g., Digital Twin), and (ii) the calculation of the ATL of the device based on a set of attributes, which are attested using the attestation enablers of ENTRUST based on evidence collected by the monitoring capabilities of the device. Then, the ATL is compared to the RTL in order to determine if the device is in a trustworthy state.

Motivation: In the context of a large-scale medical organization environment, it is imperative that the trustworthiness of all assets of the Service Graph Chain (SGC) can be verified dynamically during runtime, so that the provision of continuous, secure, and uninterrupted healthcare services is ensured throughout the operational lifecycle of each device. Thus, the Trust Assessment process employed by ENTRUST needs to be able to provide assessments on the trustworthiness level of devices dynamically during runtime in a timely manner, in order to ensure that any deviations from the correct and expected state of the devices are detected and the appropriate mitigation measures can be applied.

Building Blocks: As previously outlined, following the execution of an attestation enabler, the ATL of the device is calculated in order to determine whether it is acceptable compared to the RTL of the device. If $ATL > RTL$, the device is deemed trustworthy and a Conformity Certificate for the device is issued. Conversely, if $ATL < RTL$, the device is deemed untrustworthy, and any issued Conformity Certificate is revoked. Afterwards, the traces that led to the failed attestation are forwarded to the Digital Twin so that a simulation of the potential attack can be performed, and to determine the appropriate mitigation measures. As a result, any identified threats are sent to the Blockchain ledger to be recorded, new attestation challenges are determined, and the Protection Profile of the device is updated accordingly to include these challenges.

4.2.3 Software Verification

STORY-I: As a software service provider, I want to analyse any software for software bugs and vulnerabilities prior to the deployment on the system.

Objective: As previously mentioned, we want to find security issues as soon as possible, so these can be solved at a lower cost. This means that security checks should be done during the development of a product at the side of the manufacturer, in the design phase. This leads to the need to create a pre-deployment strategy regarding software verification that searches for known issues after the device has left the manufacturing floor. By doing this, a developer is able to patch a security issue, before it gets to the production.

Motivation: In the context of CMD it is detrimental to verify the software that is deployed into the system of a healthcare application before it reaches out the clients, be it doctors or patients. This allows for the assessment of RTL of a specific piece of software. If a security issue is found in the development phase, the cost of fixing it is much lower than the cost of fixing it after the deployment has been done.

Building Blocks: Software verification module is using YARA to scan binaries for malicious patterns that could hurt the whole system. This allows for the verification of not only the software products that are built in-house by the manufacturer, but also for 3rd party modules, such as libraries that are used. This system can easily be integrated into a DevOps pipeline allowing a software service provider to create a secure workflow that can increase the overall security of the products that one offers. This will also allow for the assessment of the ATL by integrating the software verification module into current pipelines or test suites. When a patch is deployed this can be verified again to assess if the patch actually increases the ATL and to check if it is closer to the RTL.

STORY-II: As a software service provider, I want to be able to react efficiently to any misbehaviour identified with the provision of the appropriate patches.

Objective: As mentioned in previous paragraphs, in the CMD infrastructure the need of verification. This leads to another need: when a misbehaviour is identified, the software service provider should react in a timely manner with a patch. After a patch has been identified, it needs to be deployed to all affected devices.

Motivation: If a vulnerability has been identified, this will negatively impact ATL, that is calculated by the Trust Assessment component, based on the attestation evidence. After the comparison with the RTL, it is sent to the Digital Twin. This will determine if a patch is needed. A patch that fixes that issue will increase the ATL, meaning that the software component trustworthiness is higher. This should work in both pre-deployment environments, via patches that come before the software reaches the client, and at run-time, using secure software updates.

Building Blocks: When a security issue has been found by the software verification module, this constitutes an indication of risk which is sent to the Risk Assessment module and signifies the need for a patch to be deployed. In the context of CMDs this might lead to the loss of trust of multiple devices from a network. If a patch can be made available before deployment or a secure software update is made available after during the run-time, this should be applied to all supported devices. This can lead to an increase in ATL. If the $ATL > RTL$, then it means that the trustworthiness of a device has been restored and it can be trusted again.

4.3 Threat Modelling Architecture and Flow

4.3.1 Architecture

Figure 4.3.1 illustrates the architecture of the threat modelling module of ENTRUST. This system integrates diverse sources of intelligence to create a comprehensive threat detection. Stable intelligence sources such as MITRE ATT&CK [17] provide a foundational knowledge base for known attack patterns and techniques. Complementing these are up-to-date intelligence sources, which include information scraped from news outlets and forums, ensuring real-time awareness of emerging threats.

The Large Language Model has two different roles. At first, it's used as a natural data processor, used to correlate disparate data streams, such as threat intelligence and device data. The main reason for using a LLM is that language and communication styles are inherently different between these sources: stable intelligence sources, use a communication style focused on security professionals, news and forums use a more informal communication style and device datasheets are oriented towards engineers. This makes a simple Natural Language Processing (NLP) model unsuitable since NLPs are specialized on one type of communication style or language. The second role of the LLM is that of text data generator, used for creating threat vectors and attack scenarios. This is done by using the processed threat intelligence and applying it on a specific device, to find the most relevant attacks. The LLM is designed to be used in house, so no 3rd parties are going to receive sensitive data.

Event triggers are used to optimize resources usage, by creating threat models only at specific times.

Figure 4.3.1 Threat Modelling Architecture

4.3.2 Workflow

The flow is divided into two phases: data collection and threat modelling phase.

In the initial phase the system is gathering data regarding threat landscape, using the web scraper. Afterwards, data is used by the LLM to create context or to fine-tune it. Upon completion of the data processing, the structured Threat Intelligence is conveyed to the TI Database. This database acts as a repository that stores and organizes the refined intelligence, making it accessible for further analysis.

In the threat modelling phase, the LLM receives data regarding a specific device and, using the threats that have been previously identified, creates a threat model that is sent further to the risk assessment module.

The sequence diagram of the workflow can be seen in Figure 4.3.2.

Figure 4.3.2 Threat Modelling Sequence Diagram

4.3.3 Integration with Risk Assessment

Threat modelling module provides natural language output suitable for a human user, but this kind of data cannot be efficiently processed by a machine. To keep the module friendly for an end-user, while also being able to return a result that can be easily handled by another computer process, Threat Modelling module is also connected to two additional data sources: NIST National Vulnerability Database [18] and MITRE’s Common Weakness Enumeration [19]:

- **NIST NVD** is a known database containing vulnerabilities and data regarding the devices or software that can be targeted by a specific vulnerability, such as Common Platform Enumeration (CPE).
- **MITRE CWE** is a database containing regarding attack methods. This allows for way of categorizing attacks and the relationships between them.

By combining these two additional datasets, we aim to provide a systematic way, that allows a machine to process data regarding the model. The architecture, containing the additional data sources can be seen in Figure 4.3.3.

Figure 4.3.3 Architecture with the additional data sources

Threat Modelling Module, at first queries the NIST NVD using their API to receive CVEs. These CVEs contain CWE and CPE identifiers. Based on these, the threat modelling module is processing the CWE DB file from MITRE to receive data regarding attack methods and Common Attack Pattern Enumeration and Classification (CAPEC) identifiers. These are used to create a JSON file that is sent in the end to the Risk Assessment module. This flow can be seen in Figure 4.3.4.

Figure 4.3.4 Sequence diagram containing the new data sources

4.4 Threat Intelligence Extraction

Threat Intelligence extraction is a multi-layered approach designed to filter, analyse, and refine data into a format that is directly applicable to threat identification and response strategies.

In the initial stage, raw data is harvested from a multitude of sources. These sources are broadly categorized into two types: stable and up to date. Stable sources include established databases and structured feeds that provide a stable bedrock of known threats and vulnerabilities. Up to date sources augment this by continuously scanning the digital landscape—news sites, forums, and other relevant platforms—for the latest and most immediate threat data. This ensures that the intelligence extraction process benefits from both historical and emergent threat information.

The harvested data undergoes a synthesis process by using an LLM. The LLM applies fine-tuning techniques to make the LLM give specific results regarding the current threat landscape. This step is used to reduce noise and to enhance the quality of the threat intelligence. Subsequently, the processed data is structured into a standardized format, which encapsulates the critical attributes of the threat landscape in a manner that is conducive to further analysis.

4.5 Threat Modelling Status

The threat modelling system has achieved significant progress with the successful implementation of local Large Language Model, as can be seen in Figure 4.5.1. This allows the processing of sensitive data, ensuring enhanced privacy and security compliance. The currently implemented endpoints allow for the analysis of a device and for managing the LLMs. The focus will shift towards refining the threat modelling methodology and its integration with the Risk Assessment module. Another focus will be leveraging Docker Compose to optimize deployment.

Figure 4.5.1 Status of threat modelling

An example of a request sent to the local LLM can be seen in Figure 4.5.2, where we’ve used a firmware vulnerability that was found recently to see how it could be used to attack a controller.

Figure 4.5.2 Finding an attack scenario for a recent vulnerability via LLM API

In parallel, the Threat Intelligence Extraction Status has reached a new efficacy with the integration of data from the MITRE ATT&CK database via a web scraper, as can be seen in Figure 4.5.3. The next phase will expand the system’s capabilities to include collecting data from unstructured data sources, thereby broadening the spectrum of threat intelligence, and reinforcing the overall security framework.

Figure 4.5.3 Status of threat intelligence extraction

4.6 Software Verification Architecture and Flow

4.6.1 Architecture

The role of this module is to check the safety of software applications. In the context of ENTRUST this means software that is running on the CMD, but also libraries that are used during development. Figure 4.6.1 illustrates our initial architecture for the software verification module.

The module is using Indices of Compromise from multiple intelligence sources to create a testing plan based on threat landscape. This is then applied to the existing tests, source code and binary code.

The software verification module itself is composed of a binary code analyser and a source code analyser. These are used to check if the provided files or binaries have vulnerabilities or present malicious patterns. The verification results are then sent to be visualized in a user-friendly manner and further to other modules. The software verification also outputs a JSON response containing the analysis results if one wants to process it further.

Figure 4.6.1 Software verification initial architecture

4.6.2 Workflow

The workflow starts by receiving IOCs from multiple sources and processing them. After its done processing, a user sends files or binaries that need to be verified. These can be files or binaries developed in-house or can be binaries received from 3rd parties, that needs to be verified to not introduce malicious applications that compromise the whole system. Afterwards, the software verification module does static analysis and runs the tests. Finally, the result is sent to the user in JSON format, and it is also sent further to interested modules.

The sequence diagram of this workflow can be seen in Figure 4.6.2.

Figure 4.6.2 Sequence diagram for software verification module

4.7 Software Verification Status

Currently we have implemented a YARA-based static analysis API, as can be seen in Figure 4.7.1.

Figure 4.7.1 Status of software verification

Our YARA engine [20] uses rules from established databases, such as the ones provided by Alien Vault or Google, to scan binaries for malicious patterns. If a pattern is found it is sent back to the user using a JSON response. Such a response can be seen in Figure 4.7.2, where a simple rule was triggered for a test binary.

Figure 4.7.2 Example of response from YARA scanner

We have also implemented a Grafana dashboard that can be used to see an overview of the scans that were performed. In Figure 4.7.3, is presented the Overview section, containing the number of passed and failed tests, as well as the triggered rules and a timeline regarding detections. In Figure 4.7.4, is presented the File Summary section. It contains statistics regarding what files have been scanned and what kind of files have been provided.

Figure 4.7.3 Overview section of Grafana dashboard

Figure 4.7.4 File Summary section of Grafana dashboard

Further we plan to explore other types of analysis that are tailored to the needs of the partners, such as code analysis.

4.8 Deployment

For an easy deployment, threat modelling and software verification modules are delivered using a docker compose.

As seen in Figure 4.8.1, docker compose file comes not only with the module developed by us but also with local versions of 3rd parties, so sensitive data won't leave the local network. This allows for an easy deployment while also preserving privacy.

Figure 4.8.1 Docker compose of the threat modelling and software verification

4.9 Functional Specifications for Threat Modelling, Software Verification, Trust & Risk Assessment

Table 2: User Stories for Threat Modelling and Software Verification

ID#	User story	I want to <Action>	So that <Reason>	Description
TM_1	Identification of attack vectors	As a system operator, I want to identify attack vectors that a malicious actor could use against my infrastructure	I can create an efficient strategy against those threats	Security administrators should create defense strategies based on attack vectors that are specific to a medical device or system infrastructure. ENTRUST Threat Modelling identifies attack vectors specific to a device, allowing for better decision making, when creating a defense strategy.
TM_2	User friendly scenarios	As a system operator, I want to get attack scenarios in a user-friendly way	I can better understand an attack vector	Security administrators should have attack scenarios in a user-friendly way, so their threat expectancies are well established. ENTRUST Threat Modelling leverages a LLM to create attack scenarios in natural language to set the expectations regarding what attacks could happen in a specific infrastructure.
TM_3	Systematic way of identifying each attack vector	As a system operator, I want to get threat modelling results in a systematic way, so I can integrate other tools	I can create a more comprehensive strategy	Threat modelling results should also be easily processable by other tools. ENTRUST Threat Modelling uses well-established databases, such as NIST NVD and MITRE CWE, to also provide systematic information regarding each attack vector.
TM_4	Extensible threat modelling	As a security admin, I want threat modelling to be easily extendible by using other existing tools	I am not locked at using only specific tools	Threat modelling results should be mapped to other results from known tools to be easily processable. ENTRUST Threat Modelling uses well-established databases, such as NIST NVD and MITRE CWE, to map attack scenarios to known identifiers.
TM_5	Up-to-date Intelligence	As a system operator, I want threat model to include the latest found vulnerabilities	I can create a strategy to defend against new attacks	Threat modelling should include new vulnerabilities, to allow a security administrator to create new defense strategies. ENTRUST Threat Modelling is using NIST NVD API to ensure that new vulnerabilities are used, so a threat model will include the latest vulnerabilities as well.
SV_1	Verification of third-party modules	As a developer, I want to make sure that third-party modules are safe	I won't introduce new vulnerabilities or malicious applications into development infrastructure	Software developers should be able to scan third-party modules, so an attack won't be able to use that module to initiate an attack. ENTRUST Software Verification is using a YARA-based solution to scan binary files for malicious patterns, to ensure that the used modules are safe.
SV_2	Easy update	As a security administrator, I want to update scanning rules or create custom rules	Development environments will be compliant to the security policies	Security administrators should be able to create custom rules so the development environment will be compliant to the security policies of the company. ENTRUST Software Verification allows the modification of current YARA rule, to better integrate Software Verification into an already existing security strategy.

ID#	User story	I want to <Action>	So that <Reason>	Description
SV_3	GUI	As a security administrator or as a developer, I want to check results of scanning in a user-friendly way	I can get a better overview of the results	Results should also be given in a user-friendly way, so one can get a better overview regarding scanned files. ENTRUST Software Verification does this by integrating InfluxDB and Grafana, to create a dashboard that contains information regarding the scanned files.
TM_SV_1	Local Network usage	As a security administrator, I want to use only local network for transfer of security information	Sensitive data won't be exposed to third parties	Sensitive data shouldn't leave the local network, so it won't be exposed to third parties. ENTRUST Threat Modelling and Software Verification does this by using tools that can run on local network, when sensitive data is involved.
TM_SV_2	Easy deployment	As a security administrator I want to easily deploy threat modelling and software verification modules	The new tools will be up and running as soon as possible	Security tools should allow for a easy deployment, so they will be able to protect the infrastructure as soon as possible. ENTRUST Threat Modelling and Software Verification does this by using Docker Compose, allowing for a quick setup.

Table 3: User Stories for Risk Assessment

ID#	User story	I want to <Action>	So that <Reason>	Description
RA_1	Asset modelling (automated)	As a system operator, I want to model various types of CMDs belonging to the network infrastructure of the target medical organization	I can capture and provide risk assessment for all types of entities that characterize the healthcare provision pipeline.	In the context of the medical domain, security administrators of a Health Delivery Organization should be able to express, in a granular manner, different types of heterogeneous CMDs, which may originate from different manufacturers and possess different types of attributes. The ENTRUST RA Engine has the capability to capture all types of assets within the organization, as well as various types of attributes.
RA_2	Asset relationship modelling (automated)	As a system operator, I want to be able to capture the interdependencies among the various assets of my medical organization	I can model the component diagram and data flows that characterize the asset graph.	It is essential that the ENTRUST RA Engine is able to model all logical, network, and data flow relationships between assets of the target medical organization domain, such as communication of CMDs with gateway devices. All these relationships enable the construction of component diagrams and flow diagrams that are necessary for the execution of the risk assessment methodologies that contribute to the calculations of the RTL and ATL values.
RA_3	Generation of trust models	As a system operator, I want to create models that capture different trust properties in the service graph chain	I can have a better overview of the relationships and nodes that need to be assessed per trust property.	Recall that, in the context of ENTRUST, medical devices may possess different types of properties which may be used in order to assess the trustworthiness state of the device. Therefore, the ENTRUST RA Engine should be able to capture all these types of properties that enable a fine-grained risk analysis.

ID#	User story	I want to <Action>	So that <Reason>	Description
RA_4	Visualization of asset graph	As a system operator, I want to be able to visualize the entire asset cartography of my organization	I can execute the necessary threat analysis for the risk assessment methodologies to be applied.	The visualization of an asset graph describing a specific trust model and scope provides the security administrator of the medical organization the capability to provide input based on which a more detailed analysis is performed in the context of the target risk methodology. This will enable the administrator to have a complete overview of the asset graph and identify all the attack paths and threat scenarios in an efficient manner.
RA_5	Up-to-date intelligence	As a system operator, I want to have access to the latest open intelligence information available related to threats and vulnerabilities	I can associate them with the monitored assets and evaluate their impact on the risk assessment.	In the context of threat analysis, it is necessary for the ENTRUST RA Engine to have access to the latest open intelligence information from publicly available repositories (e.g., the National Vulnerability Database). This enables an accurate identification of the security posture of the security posture of the monitored CMDs. In addition, the knowledge base should be enhanced with information of cybersecurity threat intelligence information associated with medical devices. In this regard, the security administrator should be able to provide information on known threats and vulnerabilities associated with their organization domain and should be able to provide an initial proposal for mitigation controls for any new vulnerability.
RA_6	Identification of attack paths	As a system operator, I want to be able to identify the attack paths that enable the propagation of attacks across multiple assets	I can capture the cascading effects that enable an adversary to pivot from one asset to another through the exploitation of the associated vulnerabilities.	In large-scale healthcare providers and medical organizations consisting of multiple heterogeneous devices, it is possible for a malicious party to attempt to access the target asset by compromising a different asset and using it as an entry point. In this regard, the ENTRUST RA Engine should be able to provide the optimal quantification methodology for the Cumulative Risk Level (CRL) to support a more accurate calculation of the RTL and ATL values that will be used in the context of the Trust Assessment to be performed. However, it should be noted that this calculation should be performed without imposing additional constraints that are difficult to be met during runtime.
RA_7	Continuous and dynamic risk assessment	As a system operator, I want to be able to perform risk assessment periodically, as well as in an asynchronous manner	I can have the latest risk values for the entire topology following a security incident.	Following a failed attestation of a set of attributes specified by the Protection Profile of a medical device which constitutes an indication of risk, it is possible that new threats and vulnerabilities may be identified, and the Protection Profile of the device needs to be updated with additional mitigation measures to address them. In the context of ENTRUST, recall that Risk Assessment is performed at all phases of the operational lifecycle of the device: (i) the Manufacturing Phase, which entails the execution of a RA process on the device in isolation (prior to its deployment), (ii) the Pre-Deployment Phase, which includes the execution of the RA process considering the positioning of the device within the network infrastructure of the target medical organization, and (ii) the Runtime Phase which includes the execution of the RA process following a failed attestation, as aforementioned.

ID#	User story	I want to <Action>	So that <Reason>	Description
RA_8	Modelling security controls	As a system operator, I want to be able to associate CMDs with security controls that address – fully or partially – specific risks	I can enable the calculation of impact in the risk analysis when optimal sets of mitigation mechanisms are in place.	ENTRUST offers various types of security (attestation) controls that are able to mitigate different types of vulnerabilities. Thus, when a new threat or vulnerability is identified, the appropriate mitigation strategy is determined based on the available security measures. Afterwards, the Protection Profile of the device is updated in order to include the appropriate attestation actions to be performed for the mitigation of the identified threats.
RA_9	Dynamic recalculation of RTL	As a security operator, I want to be able to recalculate the overall risk of the topology (representing a service graph chain) when new vulnerabilities are discovered from any collected trustworthiness evidence, e.g., following an attestation report	I can recalculate the TRL and communicate it to the Trust Assessment component.	In the Risk Assessment process performed during the Design phase, an initial value of the Required RTL is calculated based on the characteristics of the device in isolation, prior to its deployment to the network infrastructure of the target medical organization. However, it is possible that evidence from an attestation process may be used in order to perform recalculation of the RTL during runtime, where more evidence on the infrastructure is collected. This may afterwards be considered by the Trust Assessment component in order to compare it against the calculated ATL to evaluate if the device is in a trustworthy state.
RA_10	Automation of risk assessment	As a system operator, I want to employ an automated and seamless risk assessment analysis	I can achieve the maximum level of automation on the calculation of both ATL and RTL.	The ENTRUST Risk Assessment engine needs to be applied in medical organizations with regard to the asset topology, the associated threats, and their impact on identified damage scenarios, in order to perform a RA that considers attack path calculation and interdependencies between assets. Thus, security administrators need to provide a high volume of information in this regard. The ENTRUST RA Engine should achieve the maximum level of automation that enables a seamless risk analysis, while also allowing for adjustments and parametrization by security experts.
RA_11	Convergence of risk results	As a system operator, I want to converge outputs from both qualitative and quantitative risk quantification models	I can provide a more comprehensive RA process tailored to the set of trust properties of interest.	As previously outlined, in the context of ENTRUST, we envision the consideration of multiple types of trust attributes in order to evaluate the trustworthiness of a CMD. In this regard, the modularity of the ENTRUST RA Engine envisions the capability for the inclusion of enriched Risk Assessment methodologies, potentially better tailored to the appropriate trust properties of interest. Having the maximum level of convergence allows for a transparent risk assessment framework where multiple different results can be compared across methodologies based on a common scale (either qualitative or quantitative). It should be noted that this process may lead to loss of information, but this is a trade-off that needs to be considered by the security administrator when performing the security analysis of their organization infrastructure.

Table 4: User Stories for Trust Assessment

ID#	User story	I want to <Action>	So that <Reason>	Description
TA_1	Trust Assessment component	As a system operator, I want to be able to assess the level of trustworthiness of entities operating within the target medical organization	I am able to evaluate whether the level of trustworthiness of those entities is acceptable, or if mitigation measures need to be taken in order to increase their trustworthiness level.	The Trust Assessment component of ENTRUST is a conceptually reactive software system that receives incoming messages that provide updates about the trustworthiness of the surrounding environment or relevant entities. These are then processed and integrated into an internal representation of trust sources, trust opinions, and relationships as part of trust models. It also provides other entities with access to its trustworthiness assessment based on these internal representations and derived information. In the context of the ENTRUST framework, this component is responsible for the calculation of the ATL of the properties attested during the execution of an attestation scheme, and its comparison with the RTL in order to evaluate whether any additional action is needed.
TA_2	Trust Model Manager	As a system operator, I want to be able to have access to all type of needed Trust Model templates	I am able to express and specify all relevant information for the calculation	The Trust Model Manager is a component of the Trust Assessment module, which is responsible for managing Trust Model Templates and Trust Model Instances. These templates are application-specific, created during design-time, and specify all relevant information for the instantiation of the Trust Model Instances. It informs the Trust Assessment module about which data is needed by the application in order to run a specific function, i.e., the calculation of the ATL. In addition, the Trust Model Template specifies the relevant Trust Objects, Trust Model Instantiation Policies, Trust Relationships, Trust Sources, and Trust Methods. The Trust Model Instances are created during runtime based on the Trust Model templates, and are used in order to store trust opinions and ATLs calculated during runtime.
TA_3	Trust Source Manager	As a system operator, I want to have a method that enables the management of all available trust sources	I am able to perform Trust Assessment on the attributes specified in the Protection Profile using information from the appropriate trust sources.	The Trust Source Manager is a component of the Trust Assessment module, which is responsible for managing the available trust sources, which provide evidence about the trustworthiness of an attested property, as specified by the Protection Profile. To this end, a Trust Source Quantifier is employed in order to calculate an atomic trust opinion based on the collected evidence. This is performed based on templates that describe how the evidence should be interpreted, and contain the corresponding formulas and calculation rules for calculating the belief, disbelief, and uncertainty of the atomic trust opinion.
TA_4	Trustworthiness Level Expression Engine	As a system operator, I want to have the appropriate means for calculating and expressing the trustworthiness level of the target device	A decision can be made on the trustworthiness level based on rigorous mathematical models and processes.	The trustworthiness level is calculated by the Trustworthiness Level Expression Engine, TLEE, which is a component of the Trust Assessment module responsible for assessing the trustworthiness on the level of the trust model. The TLEE possesses the required modules in order to calculate the trust opinion for the entire trust network and calculate the ATL for the attributes specified by the Protection Profile and attested by the remote attestation processes of ENTRUST.

ID#	User story	I want to <Action>	So that <Reason>	Description
TA_5	Trust Decision Engine	As a system operator, I want to be able to make trust decisions based on the available information	I can evaluate whether the ATL of the specified attributes is higher than the RTL so that they can be deemed trustworthy.	The Trust Assessment module possesses a Trust Decision Engine component, TDE, that is responsible for making decisions on the trustworthiness of a node or set of data by comparing the ATL with the RTL, thus determining if the attributes attested are trustworthy or not. Note that while a trust decision is made by comparing the ATL with the RTL, it is also possible to make a decision by comparing their projected probabilities and checking if $P(ATL) > P(RTL)$. However, whether this method is more effective for making trust decisions is a subject of future work.
TA_6	Trust Assessment Manager	As a system operator, I want a method that is responsible for the orchestration of all tasks pertaining to the trust assessment process	I can ensure that all actions related to the execution of the trust assessment are performed in a timely manner.	The Trust Assessment Manager is the internal component of the Trust Assessment module that is responsible for the orchestration of all tasks related to trust assessment. Specifically, it is responsible for (i) providing the trust assessment service functionalities to applications (including application session management), (ii) processing and incorporating changes of trust model instances when indicated by the Trust Model Manager of the Trust Source Manager, (iii) scheduling of TLEE computations, and (iv) scheduling of TDE function calls.

4.10 Conclusions and Next Steps

ENTRUST's threat modelling module, as depicted in Figure 4.3.1, has successfully integrated a diverse array of intelligence sources to establish a comprehensive threat detection system. This system utilizes stable intelligence sources like the MITRE ATT&CK database for foundational knowledge and couples it with real-time data from news outlets and forums, ensuring a thorough awareness of both existing and emerging threats. The dual role of the in-house Large Language Model as both a natural data processor and a text data generator allows the system to process data, that has different communication styles, and to generate attack scenarios that are specific to a device.

The system's status, shown in Figure 4.5.1, reflects the successful implementation of local LLMs and Threat Modelling APIs, which facilitate device analysis and model management. The upcoming focus is set on refining the threat modelling methodology and fortifying its integration with the Risk Assessment module. In conjunction with this, the adoption of Docker Compose is anticipated to enhance deployment processes.

Simultaneously, as illustrated in Figure 4.5.3, the Threat Intelligence Extraction's efficacy has been amplified with the incorporation of data from the MITRE ATT&CK database via a web scraper. The subsequent phase aims to extend the system's capability to assimilate data from unstructured sources, thus enriching the threat intelligence spectrum and solidifying the security infrastructure further.

The software verification architecture, as initially outlined in Figure 4.6.1, has been utilizing Indices of Compromise from various intelligence sources to construct a testing plan that aligns with the threat landscape. This architecture encompasses both binary and source code analysers to detect vulnerabilities or malicious patterns, with results conveyed in a user-friendly manner.

As Figure 4.7.1 indicates, the status of software verification includes a YARA-based static analysis API. This engine scrutinizes binaries against established database rules for malevolent patterns, returning findings in a structured JSON response, as evidenced in Figure 4.7.2. Additionally, a Grafana dashboard, shown in Figure 4.7.3 and Figure 4.7.4, offers a comprehensive overview and detailed file summary of the scans performed.

Next steps involve expanding the analysis spectrum to include code analysis, tailored to partner needs. This evolution will further enhance the verification process, providing a more granular approach to identifying potential security threats within the codebase.

5 Trust Abstractions and Protection Profiles

Trust Abstractions in ENTRUST encapsulate the essential elements of security, integrity, and reliability, providing a simplified perspective on trust while maintaining a high level of robustness. These abstractions align closely with Protection Profiles and extended Manufacturer Usage Descriptions, eMUDs, facilitating a coherent approach to CMD security. Protection Profiles define the foundational security requirements for various CMDs, outlining the necessary operational characteristics to mitigate threats and ensure safe interaction within a network. They are the building blocks for a secure environment, providing a blueprint that Trust Abstractions can distill into broader concepts. This correlation allows network administrators to apply security measures at a higher level, knowing they are grounded in comprehensive and well-defined Protection Profiles. eMUDs take the concept further by specifying expected behavior for CMDs, translating Protection Profiles into enforceable policies that govern device activity. These extended MUDs act as a bridge between the technical definitions in Protection Profiles and the abstract concepts of trust. They enable automated enforcement of security rules, allowing devices to operate within a trusted framework while facilitating easier assessment and verification of security compliance.

The state of the art in MUD and its extension, eMUD, reflects a progressive enhancement in IoT security protocols. Matheu et al. (2019) [21] contributed significantly by extending MUD profiles through an automated IoT security testing methodology, highlighting the evolution of MUD applications to ensure IoT devices operate within their intended network boundaries by dynamically adapting to security test results. This work emphasizes the importance of continuous security validation in the rapidly evolving IoT landscape. García et al. (2024) [22] further advanced the application of MUD by integrating it into the modelling of cyber-physical systems, underscoring the standard's versatility beyond conventional IoT devices. This integration facilitates a more holistic approach to securing interconnected systems, ensuring that both digital and physical components adhere to prescribed network behaviors, thus mitigating potential cyber-physical threats. Sajjad et al. (2020) [23] introduced eMUD, an enhancement of the traditional MUD framework, specifically designed to counteract the proliferation of IoT botnets. By addressing vulnerabilities in home Wi-Fi routers and providing a more robust mechanism for IoT device authentication and configuration, eMUD represents a significant step forward in preventing devices from being exploited for malicious purposes. This adaptation of MUD showcases the standard's adaptability to address specific security challenges within the IoT ecosystem. Together, these works illustrate the dynamic evolution of MUD and eMUD, showcasing their critical role in securing diverse IoT and cyber-physical systems against an ever-expanding array of cybersecurity threats.

Building upon these foundations, the BoDMitM system, developed by Hadi, Sajjad, and Nisa (2019) [24], represents a novel application of MUD in botnet detection and mitigation. This system is capable of autonomously identifying botnet activities, notifying device owners, and obstructing malicious traffic with a remarkable 99% accuracy rate. Such a system exemplifies the practical application of MUD in bolstering the security of IoT devices against complex cyber threats. Additionally, the work of Feraudo et al. (2023) [25] introduces an innovative system that merges MUD with the extended Berkeley Packet Filter (eBPF) and iptables to enforce traffic filtering and rate-limiting rules. This setup effectively counters IoT botnet DDos attacks, ensuring minimal disruption to legitimate network traffic and maintaining home gateway integrity. This fusion of MUD with advanced traffic management technologies like eBPF and iptables illustrates the evolving effectiveness of MUD frameworks in combating network-based attacks within IoT ecosystems, signifying a pivotal development in IoT security.

Building on the state-of-the-art advancements in Manufacturer Usage Description and its extensions, the ENTRUST project aims to transcend current methodologies by pioneering the development of Extended MUDs specifically tailored for connected medical devices. The unique

proposition of ENTRUST lies in its commitment to encapsulate not only the static security properties traditionally associated with MUD frameworks but to ambitiously integrate dynamic security elements that adapt in real-time to the evolving threat landscape of healthcare IoT. In the context of connected medical devices, static security properties, such as device identification and baseline functionality protocols, are fundamental. However, the dynamic nature of cyber threats necessitates a more fluid and responsive approach to this end ENTRUST project aspires to set a new benchmark for IoT security within the healthcare sector. The envisioned eMUDs will not only fortify connected medical devices against current cyber threats but will also provide a scalable and adaptable framework.

5.1 Objectives and Context

In the contemporary landscape of healthcare technology, ensuring the security and reliability of connected medical devices is not just a matter of safeguarding data and systems but is intrinsically linked to the physical well-being of patients. Trust in this context is multidimensional, spanning the assurance that devices will behave predictably under varying conditions and that they will be resistant to both cyber and physical threats. These challenges are exacerbated by the current operational paradigm of "set it and forget it," where devices are deployed with the expectation of autonomous functionality without continuous oversight. The need for runtime assurance stems from the acknowledgment that threats evolve, and the conditions under which devices operate can change unpredictably. Traditional MUD profiles provide a basis for this assurance during the design phase by defining intended device behaviours and communication patterns. However, they fall short in addressing behaviours that emerge during the operational phase of a device's lifecycle. Therefore, the context we operate within mandates a robust framework that can extend the foundational security assurances offered by MUDs into the dynamic and often unpredictable realm of runtime operation. This includes developing mechanisms for continuous verification and validation, secure firmware updates, and software patching, which are crucial for maintaining the integrity and trustworthiness of the healthcare supply chain. The overarching goal is to construct a multi-faceted trust abstraction framework that encapsulates the entire lifecycle of connected medical devices. By integrating extended MUD profiles, we aim to establish a continuous trust verification process, thereby creating a proactive security posture that adapts to the shifting landscape of threats and operational challenges.

5.2 Engineering Stories

STORY-I: As a Service Provider, I want to monitor and attest during runtime only the properties that are crucial to the device's trust state and cannot be verified through Formal Verification.

Objective:

Develop a robust monitoring and attestation system capable of verifying runtime properties that embody the trust state of medical devices, ensuring these properties align with the trust model but remain agile for elements that cannot be formalized, such as dynamic behaviour or unforeseen vulnerabilities, enhancing the security and reliability of the healthcare infrastructure.

Motivation:

Ensure the continuous integrity and trustworthiness of medical devices throughout their lifecycle. Given the ever-evolving landscape of cybersecurity threats and the critical nature of healthcare services, there is a pressing need for a system that can dynamically attest to the security state of a device beyond its initial formal verification. A trust model, in this context, represents a structured approach to defining, verifying, and maintaining the security and integrity of CMDs. It sets the framework for what should be formally verified and what requires ongoing monitoring and runtime

attestation. This robust model empowers service providers with the capacity to anticipate and respond to real-time security events, safeguarding patient data and services against emergent risks.

Building Blocks:

The procedure starts with the development of trust models for CMDs that are rigorously validated for security and privacy conformance throughout the CMD lifecycle. It then incorporates a constant risk assessment method to navigate the evolving threats within the healthcare environment. This is complemented by identifying essential runtime defense gaps within the eMUDs, which require robust attestation methods such as remote attestation to ensure devices operate securely and trustworthily within their healthcare ecosystems.

STORY-II: As a Domain Manager, I want to verify the authenticity and integrity of an eMUD.

Objective:

This story focuses on equipping the Domain Manager with the capability to verify the authenticity and integrity of an eMUD. The Domain Manager's role involves validating this certification to confirm that the eMUD adheres to the specified standards and has not been tampered with. This process involves checking the eMUD against the certification authority's digital signatures or certification hashes. Successful verification ensures that the device's usage and security configurations are in line with the manufacturer's original specifications and the certification authority's stringent standards, maintaining the ecosystem's integrity.

Motivation:

This story is rooted in the imperative need to establish a secure and trustworthy environment within the medical domain's infrastructure. The integrity and authenticity of device configurations, as specified by the eMUD, are critical for maintaining operational security and reliability. By verifying the eMUD through the corresponding Certification Authority, the Domain Manager ensures that the device has not only been vetted by the manufacturer but also by a reputed third-party authority, adding an additional layer of security and trust. This acts as a benchmark for device integrity, helping to prevent the deployment of compromised or unauthorized devices within the network. The Domain Manager's ability to validate this certification is key to fostering a secure, compliant, and efficient operational environment, mitigating risks associated with device vulnerabilities and unauthorized access.

Building Blocks:

The Domain Manager integrates an eMUD Verification Service, which follows a systematic procedure to ensure the security and integrity of device configurations. Initially, the service retrieves an eMUD from the eMUD File Server, focusing specifically on the configuration data relevant to a particular device. After acquiring the eMUD, the Domain Manager employs its Certification Authority Interface to secure the necessary digital signatures or hashes that correlate with the eMUD. These signatures or hashes are crucial for the integrity verification process. The Domain Manager's Verification Engine then evaluates the eMUD against this certification data to confirm its authenticity and integrity, ensuring the device's configuration meets trusted specifications. If the verification succeeds, the Domain Manager proceeds to translate the eMUD and deploys the device into the network, ensuring that it operates in accordance with the certified guidelines.

5.3 Analysis of MUD Profiles

The Analysis of MUDs is crucial in understanding their role and limitations within the context of the ENTRUST project. MUDs are fundamental to the initial trust establishment for connected devices as they describe the ideal communication patterns and behaviours of these devices. By doing so, they provide a baseline against which network activity can be monitored and deviations can be detected. However, the static nature of MUDs means that they are primarily designed for the design and deployment phases of a device's lifecycle, with limited applicability in post-deployment scenarios.

In analysing the MUD profiles, we must first acknowledge their strengths. MUDs enable network administrators to quickly understand the intended operation of a device and to configure network policies that allow for that operation while blocking unintended and potentially malicious activities. This facilitates a "whitelist" approach to network security, greatly reducing the attack surface of the network by limiting device interactions strictly to those that are necessary for the device's function. Despite these strengths, our analysis has identified critical gaps. Most notably, MUDs do not account for the dynamic nature of trust and behaviour in connected medical devices. They are not equipped to handle the unpredictability of device behaviour that may result from firmware updates, evolving threat landscapes, and the complexities introduced by the interaction of multiple devices within the healthcare ecosystem. Furthermore, they do not inherently provide mechanisms for updating or revising device behaviour profiles as the operational context changes over time.

To address these shortcomings within the ENTRUST framework, it is imperative to extend the concept of MUDs to encompass runtime behaviour and trust reassessment. This involves not only the consideration of static device properties and behaviours but also dynamic and potentially anomalous behaviours that could indicate a security threat or a deviation from trusted operation. The analysis of current MUD profiles underscores the necessity for a more dynamic and adaptive approach. This approach must integrate real-time data, continuous trust assessment, and the ability to respond to emergent behaviours and threats. Such an approach would not replace MUDs but would enhance them, creating what we refer to as eMUDs within the ENTRUST project.

5.4 MUD Profiles in ENTRUST

5.4.1 MUD Extended Sections

In the context of the ENTRUST project, the eMUDs represent a significant enhancement to the security management of connected medical devices. These extensions are not merely incremental; they are a reconceptualization of device descriptions that cater to the dynamic and complex nature of modern healthcare environments. The security properties included in the eMUDs are expansive and adaptive, providing a more nuanced and responsive approach to device security. They enable devices to operate within a security framework that is not rigid but is capable of adapting to new threats as they emerge. This adaptability is crucial in an era where threats evolve rapidly and often elude traditional, static forms of protection.

The weakness and vulnerability management aspect of eMUDs serves as a comprehensive approach to understanding and mitigating risks. It is not simply a repository of potential flaws but a dynamic, regularly updated system that reflects the current security landscape. By integrating this into the eMUD structure, stakeholders are empowered with actionable intelligence about the devices they depend on. This ongoing process of cataloguing and updating known vulnerabilities is critical to maintaining trust and ensuring that swift action can be taken when issues arise.

The eMUDs' "additional properties based on security properties" field is an innovative and flexible structure developed in the context of the ENTRUST project, designed to hold an array of advanced security descriptors. These descriptors are meticulously selected to address the known

and potential security challenges faced by medical devices in real-world scenarios. This field is intentionally dynamic, allowing for the integration of properties as they are identified and validated by the security community and industry stakeholders. The "weaknesses" and "vulnerabilities" fields in eMUDs serve a critical function, operating as live databases that document the specific frailties of medical devices. Each weakness and vulnerability are recorded with an identifier, a descriptive name, an exhaustive description, the date of identification, the likelihood of exploitation, the associated risk level, and a Common Vulnerability Scoring System rating. This detailed record-keeping is pivotal for proactive risk management, enabling stakeholders to prioritize responses and deploy resources effectively.

The eMUDs' approach within ENTRUST signals a departure from the static, compliance-based models of the past. It acknowledges that the security of connected medical devices is an ever-evolving challenge that demands a proactive and agile response, aligning with the project's dedication to ensuring patient safety and data integrity in the face of an increasingly sophisticated threat environment.

5.4.2 Exploitation of eMUDs in the Context of ENTRUST

The utilization of an NGINX server in the ENTRUST project for deploying eMUDs is a strategic choice, enhancing the project's capability to manage the security of connected medical devices in real-time. The NGINX server acts as a robust, high-performance host that ensures eMUDs are accessible and updated, providing a reliable point of reference for the Tracer to perform continuous and thorough monitoring. The Tracer, by continuously comparing real-time device behaviour against the eMUD profiles, ensures compliance with security expectations and trust models. Simultaneously, the eMUD Manager's role is instrumental in the proactive adaptation of eMUDs, allowing for an agile response to new threat intelligence and changes in device behaviour patterns. This setup exemplifies a proactive, adaptive approach to security, essential for maintaining the stringent trust and safety standards required in healthcare technology. The NGINX server's role in this architecture underscores the ENTRUST project's commitment to employing leading-edge technologies to advance healthcare device security.

During the runtime phase, as shown in Figure 5.3.1, a series of interactions occur between different components to achieve a secure environment. The process initiates when the CMD sends an eMUD URL to the Domain Manager. Upon receipt, the Domain Manager requests the eMUD from the MUD Server. In turn, the MUD Server responds by sending the eMUD back to the Domain Manager. The Domain Manager is then tasked with verifying the eMUD, ensuring that it is authentic and intact. After successful verification, the Domain Manager extracts the policies and runtime assurance claims from the eMUD.

Figure 5.4.1 - Runtime flow for the ENTRUST eMUD profile

These policies are then enforced, ensuring that the device operates within the security parameters set by the manufacturer, as defined in the eMUD profile. This mechanism allows for automated, dynamic policy enforcement that is tailored to each specific IoT device, reducing the overhead for network administrators and enhancing the overall security posture. The extended MUD profiles serve as a foundational element in ENTRUST’s security framework, enabling the creation of device certificates and signed MUD files that are essential for the MUD phase. They provide a structured and standard approach to defining permissible behaviour for IoT devices, which is crucial for maintaining the integrity and security of the network. The profiles also facilitate the automation of security policy implementation, reducing the potential for human error and the resources required for manual configuration.

5.5 Functional Specifications for Trust Abstraction Profile

Table 5: User Stories for Trust Abstraction Profile

ID#	User story	I want to <Action>	So that <Reason>	Description
TAP_1	eMUD profile creation	As a CMD manufacturer, I want to know the security properties and additional information required to be included in the eMUD profiles,	I can define the corresponding fields in the eMUD profiles files.	CMD manufacturers seek to understand the security properties and additional information necessary for inclusion in the eMUD profiles, aiming to accurately define the corresponding fields within the eMUD profile files. These fields are essential for the rest of the components that their functionality relies on the information included in the eMUDs.

ID#	User story	I want to <Action>	So that <Reason>	Description
TAP_2	eMUD Continuous Assessment	Integrate continuous trust verification	Adapt to the shifting landscape of threats and operational challenges	Integrate continuous trust verification in the eMUD profiles to address dynamic and potentially anomalous behaviors that could indicate security threats or deviations from trusted operation. This approach extends beyond traditional MUD profiles to accommodate runtime behavior and trust reassessment.
TAP_3	Monitor CMDs in real time utilizing attributes described in eMUDs.	Perform targeted monitoring pertaining to certain CMD attributes	I can detect unusual activity or security breaches, allowing for immediate response to ensure the safety and security of medical devices and their data.	The tracer operates by extracting attributes from eMUDs that define expected behavior and security properties. These attributes serve as benchmarks, allowing the tracer to identify deviations from normal operation and promptly detect security threats. By focusing on these predefined attributes, the system ensures robust real-time monitoring and maintains the security and integrity of CMDs.

6 Digital Twins

In the rapidly evolving domain of healthcare technology, ensuring the security and integrity of CMDs is paramount. These systems, which are integral to modern medical practices, face a diverse range of cyber threats that can compromise patient safety, data privacy, and service continuity. To address these challenges, we aim to leverage the innovative capabilities of digital twin technology. Digital twins create dynamic, virtual replicas of physical systems, enabling real-time monitoring, analysis, and simulation of cyber threats within a safe, controlled environment. This approach not only enhances our understanding of system vulnerabilities but also enables proactive security measures and design optimization.

The integration of digital twin technology in the cybersecurity of connected medical systems represents a forefront of research and development, addressing the critical need for proactive security measures in healthcare technology. Jimenez et al. [26] discuss the adoption of Wireless Body Area Networks (WBAN) based on IoT along with cloud computing systems in healthcare, highlighting the cybersecurity challenges that arise with these technologies. The analysis emphasizes the need for deeper investigation into cybersecurity challenges as medical cyber-physical systems (MCPSs) and digital twins become more prevalent in healthcare. Pirbhulal et al. [27] propose a novel and automated framework to reinforce cybersecurity in IoT-based healthcare using digital twin technology. This framework aims to provide dynamic and adaptive security solutions to identify real-time threats and vulnerabilities, demonstrating the potential of digital twins in improving healthcare cybersecurity. Zhang and Tai [28] introduce a new medical digital twin that combines Haptic-AR navigation and deep learning techniques for secure cyber-human interaction. Their study suggests a novel scheme for recognizing and fixing vulnerabilities in medical digital twins, pointing towards the importance of cyber resilience in healthcare systems.

Upon these advancements on using digital twins in the healthcare technologies for security, the ENTRUST project aims to harness the full potential of digital twin technology to revolutionize healthcare cybersecurity practices. Our goal is to create a resilient, adaptive, and proactive security framework that not only addresses current cybersecurity challenges but also anticipates future threats. By integrating real-time monitoring, predictive analytics, and attack validation, we plan to enhance the protection of sensitive patient data and critical healthcare infrastructure. Below, we present a series of high-level user stories that illustrate our vision for employing digital twin technology to bolster the cybersecurity framework of connected medical systems. Each story highlights a specific aspect of the envisioned (proposed) solution, showcasing the potential of

digital twins to secure and manage connected medical systems. We will expand on design and implementation topics in the subsequent deliverables.

6.1 Engineering Stories

STORY-I: As a software service provider, I want to be able to keep a virtual representation of a target system, so that I continuously monitor its behaviour and enable a constant device learning (and possibly prediction) process.

Objective: Develop and maintain a dynamic digital twin solution that accurately mirrors the CMD system in real-time. This solution aims to facilitate continuous monitoring, learning, and predictive analysis of the system's behaviour and security posture. By leveraging advanced threat models to simulate potential attacks, the solution will enable software service providers to proactively identify and address vulnerabilities, ensuring the integrity and resilience of the medical system against evolving cyber threats.

Motivation: The motivation stems from the critical need to safeguard systems containing CMDs in the evolving landscape of healthcare technologies. As these systems become increasingly complex and integral to patient care, the potential impact of cybersecurity breaches escalates. Unauthorized access or disruptions can lead to compromised patient data privacy, altered medical device functionality, and, ultimately, patient harm. Traditional security measures often lag behind the rapid pace of technological advancements and cyber threat evolution. Therefore, adopting a proactive and adaptive security approach through a digital twin solution enables continuous monitoring and real-time analysis. The ultimate goal is to maintain the integrity, availability, and confidentiality of CMDs, thereby protecting patient safety and trust in healthcare technology.

Building Blocks: The trace component provides mechanisms for continuous data collection from the physical medical system, including device status, network traffic, and security events. Data will be collected during the attestation processes in the runtime phase, and digital twin will be deployed for cases $ATL < RTL$. Advanced data analytics tools are needed to process and interpret this data, facilitating ongoing learning and adaptation of the digital twin model. The digital twin component will create a real-time virtual model of the CMD by using the real-time data of the CMD collected through the trace component. This data includes accurate representations of devices, gateways, and network architectures, enabling the simulation of real-world behaviours and interactions within a controlled virtual environment. The threat modelling component integrates comprehensive threat models encapsulating potential attack vectors and vulnerabilities specific to CMDs. This component provides capabilities for simulating these threats against the digital twin, allowing for the evaluation of security posture and the identification of potential vulnerabilities before they can be exploited in the real system. We plan to leverage machine learning algorithms and predictive analytics to forecast potential vulnerabilities and suggest mitigation strategies. This involves analysing trends from past data and simulated attack outcomes to predict future security challenges. A user-friendly interface will allow software service providers to monitor the health and security status of the IoT system, view predictions of vulnerabilities, and receive recommendations for mitigation actions. This interface will support what-if analyses to evaluate the impact of proposed changes or updates to the system's design.

STORY-II: As a cybersecurity analyst in a healthcare organization, I want to be able to validate/simulate real-time cyber-attacks on the digital representation of our medical systems having CMDs so that I can understand the potential impact of various threats and evaluate the effectiveness of our current security measures.

Objective: Implement an environment within the digital twin framework to enable cybersecurity analysts to conduct detailed, real-time cyber-attacks on the virtual model of medical systems with CMDs. This environment will facilitate the identification of vulnerabilities, assessment of potential

impacts of various cyber threats, and evaluation of current security protocols' effectiveness. The goal is to leverage these insights to strengthen security measures, develop robust response strategies, and ensure the comprehensive protection of patient data and system functionality against cyber-attacks.

Motivation: The motivation is driven by the critical need to anticipate and mitigate cybersecurity threats in an increasingly digital healthcare landscape. Medical systems, essential for patient care and data management, present attractive targets for cyber attackers. The repercussions of successful attacks could be catastrophic, including breaches of sensitive patient data, disruptions to medical services, and potential harm to patient well-being. Traditional reactive security measures are no longer sufficient in this fast-evolving threat environment. By enabling cybersecurity analysts to simulate attacks in a controlled, virtual environment, organizations can gain invaluable insights into their systems' vulnerabilities and the effectiveness of their defences. This approach allows for the timely strengthening of security measures, ensuring the integrity and resilience of healthcare services and protecting patient trust and safety.

Building Blocks: At the core is the attack validation component capable of mimicking a variety of cyber-attacks based on real-world scenarios and threat intelligence. This component uses the digital twin's detailed system model to simulate attacks, assess system vulnerabilities, and predict potential impacts without risking the physical system. A comprehensive database stores, updates, and categorizes various cyber threats, vulnerabilities, attack vectors, and real-world incidents. This database feeds the simulation engine with the necessary data to execute realistic attack scenarios. The digital twin model is a high-fidelity digital representation of the target medical system, including devices, networks, and data flows. It mirrors the real system's behaviour under normal and attack conditions, allowing for accurate simulation results. The attack validation component uses the Digital Twin model to execute attack scenarios, while the outcomes are processed to identify vulnerabilities and assess defences.

STORY-III: As a system engineer responsible for the design of a connected medical system, I want to be able to input proposed design changes into a digital twin model and analyse the impact of these changes on the system's security posture. This analysis should include what-if scenarios that help identify potential vulnerabilities introduced by the design changes and evaluate the effectiveness of various security measures.

Objective: Create a comprehensive analysis framework within the digital twin environment that allows system engineers to input and assess the impact of design changes on the security of connected medical systems. This framework will support what-if scenario analyses, enabling engineers to foresee potential security vulnerabilities and assess the efficacy of countermeasures in response to proposed design modifications. The primary goal is to ensure that each design decision contributes positively to the system's overall security posture, thereby pre-emptively enhancing the system's defence mechanisms against cyber threats prior to real-world implementation.

Motivation: The motivation behind this user story arises from the increasing complexity and interconnectivity of medical systems, which amplify their vulnerability to cyber threats. In such a context, design decisions play a critical role in shaping the system's security landscape. Engineers face the challenge of not only creating efficient and reliable systems but also ensuring that these systems are resilient to cyber-attacks. Traditional design approaches, which often consider security a secondary or post-development concern, are inadequate for addressing the sophisticated and evolving nature of cyber threats. Integrating security analyses into the design phase through what-if scenario analysis and impact assessments within a digital twin framework, engineers can proactively identify and mitigate potential security vulnerabilities. This proactive approach can enhance the system's security and also can reduce the cost and effort required for

post-deployment fixes, ensuring the safety and integrity of patient data and medical services from the outset. The ultimate motivation is to foster a design culture that prioritizes security as an integral, foundational component, thereby safeguarding the healthcare ecosystem against the adverse effects of cyber-attacks.

Building Blocks: Engineers input proposed design changes into the digital twin system. The input might be architectural adjustments to the integration of new devices or software updates. The digital twin component serves the foundation for analysing design changes and their security implications. This model must be dynamic and allow real-time updates to mirror proposed design changes. By using the digital twin component, the system engineer analyses various what-if scenarios based on the input design changes. This framework evaluates the impact of these changes on the system's security by mimicking potential attack vectors and assessing the system's response to such threats. The digital twin component works in conjunction with the risk assessment component to analyse the outcomes of analysis, identifying any new vulnerabilities or weaknesses introduced by the design changes and providing a detailed analysis of potential security breaches and their implications.

7 Conclusions

As previously outlined, one of the core tenets of ENTRUST is the maintenance of the trustworthiness level of CMDs operating within a medical organization infrastructure throughout their operational lifecycle. In this deliverable, in **Chapter 2**, we first provided a high-level overview of the action workflow of the ENTRUST framework. Note that, in D2.1 [1], we provided an initial version of the reference architecture of ENTRUST. Here, we provided a more detailed version of this architecture, with particular focus on the components involved in the aforementioned process, which entails the calculation of the RTL and the ATL of a CMD in order to determine if it is in a trustworthy state. Afterwards, throughout the remainder of this deliverable, we carefully outlined the progress of the ENTRUST tasks T3.1-T3.3, detailing challenges & breakthroughs in defining the appropriate formal models and theorem proofs capturing all the cryptographic primitives to be leveraged for safeguarding the device's operation.

In **Chapter 3** (Formal Verification of Secure Device Lifecycle Management), we describe the efforts made to define a refined model of the ENTRUST onboarding phase and verify its security requirements. The VerifPal language and tool were initially used for modelling and verification, but only a simplified version was successfully verified. The ProVerif language was then utilized to demonstrate that all security properties can be verified. The next steps include expanding the model to include more attributes and verifying other aspects of device behaviour, as well as exploring different modelling and verification tools. Additionally, there is potential for designing a tool-independent notation for protocol specification.

In **Chapter 4** (Threat Modelling and Software Verification), we highlight the successful integration of diverse intelligence sources into the ENTRUST threat modelling module, allowing for comprehensive threat detection. The system combines stable intelligence sources with real-time data to stay updated on existing and emerging threats. The in-house Large Language Model plays a dual role as a data processor and text generator, enabling the system to process different communication styles and generate device-specific attack scenarios. The focus now shifts towards refining the threat modelling methodology and strengthening integration with the Risk Assessment module, alongside the adoption of Docker Compose for improved deployment processes. The incorporation of data from the MITRE ATT&CK database via a web scraper has enhanced the efficacy of Threat Intelligence Extraction, while the software verification architecture utilizes various intelligence sources to construct a testing plan and detect vulnerabilities. The next steps involve expanding the analysis to include code analysis, tailored to partner needs, in order to enhance the verification process and identify potential security threats within the codebase.

In **Chapter 5** (Trust Abstractions and Protection Profiles), it is emphasized the importance of ensuring the security and reliability of CMDs in the healthcare technology landscape, extending trust concept beyond data protection to include device behaviour and resistance to cyber and physical threats. While traditional MUD profiles provide assurance during the design phase, they lack addressing emerging behaviours during device operation. The goal is to create a multi-faceted trust abstraction framework that encompasses the entire lifecycle of connected medical devices, integrating extended MUD profiles for continuous trust verification and proactive security adaptation.

In **Chapter 6** (Digital Twins), we glance into the proposed integration of digital twin technology within the overall ENTRUST framework, illustrating its transformative potential to fortify connected medical systems against a broad spectrum of cyber threats. We explore the state-of-the-art advancements, drawing from recent scholarly research and case studies that underscore the efficacy of digital twins in real-time monitoring, vulnerability assessment, and predictive security measures. By analysing the building blocks of digital twin technology, we lay a comprehensive foundation for understanding how these components interact to enhance the security posture of CMDs in the ENTRUST framework. Additionally, we describe user stories that highlight practical applications of digital twins in both ongoing security management and pre-emptive design phase analyses.

Each task will be continued towards accomplishing the overarching objectives of WP3, as planned. The document may also serve as a guide for future readers, offering initial insights and strategies for ensuring CMD secure operations.

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Appendices

VerifPal Model

```

attacker[active]

principal Cmd[
  knows private id_p // CMD identifier
  knows private kdk // key derivation key
  knows private ak // authentication key
  generates rand_p
]

principal Aaa[
  knows private id_s // AAA identifier
  knows private kdk // key derivation key
  knows private ak // authentication key
  knows private k // encryption key
  generates rand_s
]

principal Dm[
  knows private k // encryption key
]

// New device wants to join the network

// Step 5: Send identity
Aaa -> Dm: id_s, rand_s

// Step 6: Request identity
Dm -> Cmd: id_s, rand_s

principal Cmd[
  // Compute MAC_P
  mac_p = MAC(ak, CONCAT(id_p, rand_p, id_s, rand_s))
]

// Step 7: Response Identity
Cmd -> Dm: rand_p, id_p, mac_p

// Step 8: Delegate identity verification
Dm -> Aaa: rand_p, id_p, mac_p

principal Aaa[
  // Verify MAC_P
  _ = ASSERT(MAC(ak, CONCAT(id_p, rand_p, id_s, rand_s)), mac_p)?

  // derive transient key for the protected channel and MSK
  eap_session_key_aaa, msk_aaa = HKDF(rand_p, kdk, nil)

  // Compute MAC_S
  mac_s = MAC(ak, CONCAT(id_s, rand_p))

  // Protected channel
  generates payload
  tag = MAC(eap_session_key_aaa, CONCAT(payload, rand_s))
]

```



```

]

// Step 9: Delegation response
Aaa -> Dm: mac_s, payload, tag

// Step 10: Request protected channel
Dm -> Cmd: mac_s, payload, tag

principal Cmd[
  // Verify MAC_S
  _ = ASSERT(MAC(ak, CONCAT(id_s, rand_p)), mac_s)?

  // derive transient key for the protected channel and MSK
  eap_session_key_cmd, msk_cmd = HKDF(rand_p, kdk, nil)

  // Verify tag of the protected channel
  _ = ASSERT(MAC(eap_session_key_cmd, CONCAT(payload, rand_s)), tag)?

  // Protected channel
  generates payload1
  tag1 = MAC(eap_session_key_cmd, CONCAT(payload1, rand_s))
]

// Step 11: Response protected channel
Cmd -> Dm: payload1, tag1

// Step 12: Delegate check tag
Dm -> Aaa: payload1, tag1

principal Aaa[
  // Verify tag of the protected channel tag
  _ = ASSERT(MAC(eap_session_key_aaa, CONCAT(payload1, rand_s)), tag1)?

  // Encrypt MSK
  msk_enc = ENC(k, msk_aaa)
]

// Step 13: Delegation response MSK
Aaa -> Dm: msk_enc

principal Dm[
  // Decrypt MSK
  msk_dm = DEC(k, msk_enc)
]

queries[
  confidentiality? msk_aaa
  confidentiality? eap_session_key_cmd
  confidentiality? eap_session_key_aaa
  confidentiality? ak
  confidentiality? kdk
  authentication? Dm -> Cmd: mac_s
  authentication? Dm -> Aaa: mac_p
]

```


eMUD template

```
// rfc8520
// based on YANG Modules and several related studies
"ietf-mud:mud": {
//Section general properties of mud and the iot devices
    "mud-version": 1,
    "mud-url": "http://localhost/eMud_Entrust.json",
    "mud-signature": "The location of mud signature",
    "last-update": "This is a date-and-time value of when the MUD file was
generated",
    "cache-validity": 48, //This uint8 is the period of time in hours that a
network //management station MUST wait since its last
retrieval //before checking for an update
    "is-supported": true, // This boolean is an indication from the manufacturer
to //the network administrator as to whether or not the Thing
//is supported
    "systeminfo": "Short descr. of the thing",
    "mfg-name": "The name of the manufacturer of this physical component.",
    "documentation": "This URI consists of a URL that points to documentation
relating to the device and the MUD file",
    "model-name": "The vendor-specific model name identifier string associated
with this physical component",
    "software-rev": "refers to higher-level applications or operating systems that
run on the device",
    "firmware-rev": "refers to the software that is closely linked to the hardware it runs
on",
    "security-properties": "refers to device properties",
    "os": {
        "name": "",
        "distro": "",
        "version": ""
    },
},
"cpu": {
    "type": "",
    "cores": ""
},
    "ram": {
"size": ""
},
"crypto": {
    "alg": "",
    "type": "",
    "key-size": "",
    "other": {
}
},
"network": {
    ports: [ {
        number: "",
        type: ""
    }
    ]
},
},
```



```

}, //end general properties

//section weaknesses and vulnerabilities
// extend mud by define weaknesses based on risk assessment
"weaknesses": [
{
  "id": "",
  "name": "",
  "description": "",
  "date": "",
  "likelihood": "",
  "risk": "",
  "cvss": ""
}
],

// extend mud by define vulnerabilities based on risk assessment
"vulnerabilities": [
{
  "id": "",
  "name": "",
  "description": "",
  "date": "",
  "likelihood": "",
  "risk": "",
  "cvss": ""
}
//...
],

//Treat mitigation based on stix2.1
  "threat-mitigation": [
{
  "type": "course-of-action",
  "id": "id of coa", // eg"coa--a1b2c3d4-1234-5678-abcd-1234567890ab"
  "action": "Recommended course of action ", //"Apply Vendor-Supplied Patch
for with cve-idx",
  "description": "description of action ", // "Apply the vendor-supplied
patch or update for cve-idx to mitigate the vulnerability ",
  "objective": "what is the objective", //"Mitigate the risk of exploitation
and unauthorized "
  "target-ref": "" //vulnerabilities/threats id"
}
  ],

//End Section weaknesses and vulnerabilities

//Section acls and ace

////The policies that should be enforced on traffic going from the device
"from-device-policy": {
//Each entry on this list refers to an ACL that should be present in the overall access
list data mode.
//Each ACL is identified by name ";
  "access-lists": {

```



```

        "access-list": [
            {
                "name": "mud-id-v1fr"
            }
        ]
    },
},

//The policies that should be enforced on traffic going to the device
"to-device-policy": {
    "access-lists": {
        "access-list": [
            {
                "name": "mud-id-v1to"
            }
        ]
    }
},

"ietf-access-control-list:acls": {
//RFC 8519
//An ACL is an ordered list of ACEs
//Each ACE has a list of match criteria and a list of actions.
//Since there are several kinds of ACLs implemented
//with different attributes for different vendors,
//this model accommodates customizing ACLs for
//each kind and for each vendor
"acl": [
    {
        "name": "mud-id-v1fr",
//Type of ACL. Indicates the primary intended
//type of match criteria (e.g., Ethernet, IPv4, IPv6, mixed,
//etc.) used in the list instance.
        "type": "ipv4-acl-type",
        "aces": {
            "ace": [ // Access Control Entry
                {
                    "name": "name of Ace",
//The "matches" define criteria used to identify patterns in
//"ietf- packet-fields". The choice statements within the match
//container allow for the selection of one header within each of
//"12", "13", or "14" headers. The "actions" define the
//behavior to undertake once a "match" has been identified
                    "matches": {
"mud": {
"manufacturer": {
//This node consists of a hostname that would be matched against the
//authority component of another Thing's MUD URL.
},
"same-manufacturer": {
//This null-valued node is an equivalent for when the manufacturer
//element is used to indicate that the authority found in another
//ing's MUD URL matches that of the authority found in this Thing's
//D URL
},
},
"documentation": {

```



```
//This URI consists of a URL that points to documentation relating to
//the device and the MUD file. This can prove particularly useful when
//the "controller" class is used, so that its use can be explained.
},
"12": {
//Match Layer 2 headers, for example, Ethernet
//header fields.
},
    "13": {
//Choice of either IPv4 or IPv6 headers
    },
    "14": {
//Rule set that matches TCP/UDP headers.
    },
"15": {
//?Rules for application layer
},
"keys": {
//?Encryption key specification type,size,alg
}
    },
    "actions": {
        "forwarding": "accept" //deny
    }
}
    ]
},
{
    "name": "mud-id-v1to",
    "type": "ipv4-acl-type",
    "aces": {
        "ace":[
{
//...
}
    ]
}
    ]
}
}
}
```


ProVerif Model

free c: channel.

free s: channel [private].

type key.

type randomnumber.

type payload.

fun MAC(key, bitstring): bitstring.

fun HKDF1(randomnumber, key): key.

fun HKDF2(randomnumber, key): key.

fun payloadGeneration(bitstring): bitstring.

fun skenc(key, key): bitstring.

reduc forall m: key, k: key; skdec(skenc(m,k),k) =m.

(*Query*)

free Mac_p: bitstring [private].

type host.

free Mac_a: bitstring [private].

free Mac_s: bitstring [private].

free Mac_b: bitstring [private].

free msk_aaa: bitstring [private].

free msk_CMD: bitstring [private].

free eap_session_key_CMD: bitstring [private].

free eap_session_key_aaa: bitstring [private].

free Ak: bitstring [private].

free kdk: bitstring [private].

free K: bitstring [private].

query attacker (msk_aaa).

query attacker (msk_CMD).

query attacker (eap_session_key_CMD).

query attacker (eap_session_key_aaa).

query attacker (Ak).

query attacker (kdk).

query attacker (K).

event userauthenticated(bitstring).

query event(userauthenticated(Mac_p)) ==> inj-event(userauthenticated(Mac_a)).

query event(userauthenticated(Mac_s)) ==> inj-event(userauthenticated(Mac_b)).

(* The process *)

let AAA(Id_s: bitstring, Kdk: key, Ak: key, K: key) =

(*Step 1*)

new Rand_s: randomnumber;

out (c, (Rand_s, Id_s));

(*Step 2*)

in (c, (Rand_p: randomnumber, Id_p: bitstring, Mac_p: bitstring));


```

let Concat1 = (Id_p, Rand_p, Id_s, Rand_s) in
let Mac_A = MAC(Ak, Concat1) in
if Mac_p = Mac_A then
  event userauthenticated(Mac_A);
let Concat2 = (Id_s, Rand_p) in
let Mac_s = MAC (Ak, Concat2) in
let eap_session_key_aaa = HKDF1 (Rand_p, Kdk) in
let msk_aaa = HKDF2 (Rand_p, Kdk) in
new Payload : payload;
let Concat3 = (Payload, Rand_s) in
let tag = MAC (eap_session_key_aaa, Concat3) in
out (c, (Mac_s, Payload, tag));

```

```

(*Step 3*)
in (c, (Payload1: payload, tag1: bitstring));
let Concat4 = (Payload1, Rand_s) in
let Mac_D = MAC (eap_session_key_aaa, Concat4) in
if tag1 = Mac_D then
  event userauthenticated(Mac_D);
let MSK_Enc = skenc(msk_aaa, K) in
out (c, MSK_Enc).

```

let Dm(k: key) =

```

(*Step 1*)
in (c, (Rand_s: randomnumber, Id_s: bitstring));
out (c, (Rand_s, Id_s));

```

```

(*Step 2*)
in (c, (Rand_p: randomnumber, Id_p: bitstring, Mac_p: bitstring));
out (c, (Rand_p, Id_p, Mac_p));

```

```

(*Step 3*)
in (c, (Mac_s: bitstring, Payload: payload, tag: bitstring));
out (c, (Mac_s, Payload, tag));

```

```

(*Step 4*)
in (c, (Payload1: payload, tag1: bitstring));
out (c, (Payload1, tag1));

```

```

(*Step 5*)
in (c, MSK_Enc: bitstring);
let MSK_Dm = skdec(MSK_Enc,k) in 0.

```

let CMD(Id_p: bitstring, Kdk: key, Ak: key) =

```

(*Step 1*)
in (c, (Rand_s: randomnumber, Id_s: bitstring));
new Rand_p: randomnumber;
let Concat5 = (Id_p, Rand_p, Id_s, Rand_s) in
let Mac_p = MAC(Ak, Concat5) in
out (c, (Rand_p, Id_p, Mac_p));

```



```
(*Step 2*)
in (c, (Mac_s: bitstring, Payload: bitstring, tag: bitstring));
let Concat6 = (Id_s, Rand_p) in
let Mac_b = MAC(Ak, Concat6) in
if Mac_s = Mac_b then
  event userauthenticated(Mac_b);
let eap_session_key_CMD = HKDF1(Rand_p, Kdk) in
let msk_CMD = HKDF2(Rand_p, Kdk) in
let Concat7 = (Id_s, Rand_p) in
let Mac_c = MAC(Ak, Concat7) in
if tag = Mac_c then
  event userauthenticated(Mac_c);
new Payload1 : payload;
let Concat8 = (Payload1, Rand_s) in
let tag1 = MAC(eap_session_key_CMD, Concat8) in
out (c, (Payload1, tag1)).

process
new Id_s: bitstring;
new Kdk: key;
new Ak: key;
new K: key;
new Id_p: bitstring;

((!AAA(Id_s, Kdk, Ak, K)) | (!Dm(K)) | (!CMD(Id_p, Kdk, Ak)))
```

